

RISIS

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SCIENCE
AND INNOVATION POLICY STUDIES

Register of Research and Higher Education Organizations (OrgReg) Methodological handbook January 2021

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Name
DG EAC	Directorate General Education and Culture
DG RTD	Directorate General for Research and Innovation
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Economic Area
EFTA	European Free Trade Agreement
ERA	European Research Area
ETER	European Tertiary Education Register
EUMIDA	European Microdata Project
EUROSTAT	European Statistical Office
FOS	Fields of Science
FTE	Full Time Equivalents
HC	Headcount
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Educational Degrees
ISCED-F	ISCED fields of Education and Training classification (2013)
NC	National currency
NE	National Experts
NSA	National Statistical Authority
PPP	Purchasing power parity
RFO	Research Funding Organizations
RTO	Research Technology Organizations
R&D	Research and Development
UAS	Universities of Applied Sciences
UOE	UNESCO OECD Eurostat handbook on educational statistics

1 Introduction

The register of research and higher education organizations (OrgReg) is a central facility within the Research Infrastructure for Science and Innovation Studies (RISIS) which aims at uniquely identifying and tracking over time some types of organizations involved in the research and higher education system (higher education institutions, public research organizations, research hospital, public administration entities and private non-profit organizations).

Therefore, the register covers “public” and “semi-public” organizations engaged in R&D and higher education, broadly corresponding to the Government, Higher Education and Private Non-Profit sector as identified by the Frascati manual, 2015 edition (FM 2015). Additionally, the register includes public Research Funding Organizations and Charities providing project funds to R&D performing organizations. The register excludes business enterprises oriented to the market (business enterprise sector of the FM), which will be dealt in a separate register, but includes public-private partnerships performing R&D, like some Research Technology Organizations (RTOs).

Thus, the register provides an unambiguous list of these organizations and attributes them a unique ID, based on their organizational identity, which is stable over time and can be matched with different names and identifiers used in other RISIS facilities, like the European Tertiary Education Register (ETER), the Leiden Ranking and the EUPRO database on participation to European programs.

The register is central service within RISIS for the integration and harmonization of organizations within RISIS datasets. More specifically, it fulfils following functions:

- First, it provides a reference list of organizations provided with unique organizational IDs and tracked over time for demographic changes. This reference list will allow interoperability with other RISIS datasets, which provide data on organizations, like Leiden Ranking, EUPRO and the European Tertiary Education Register, thanks to the adoption in these datasets of the reference IDs. Additionally, a reference list provides a basis for interlinking with open data available on the Internet, as well as for searching data from the Web.
- Second, OrgReg provides thanks to its integration with the KNOWMAK central database, OrgReg provides indicators on research output of research organizations (scientific publications, European projects, patents) disaggregated by region, using the NUTS regional classification of EUROSTAT.

The handbook has been constructed through an intense phase of discussion between most RISIS partners and subsequently updated based on the successive development of the register. A parallel project will deal with the implementation of a similar register for firms (FirmReg).

The handbook is constructed as follows:

- Section 2 explains the basic definitions for the register and the delimitation of the perimeter, as well as main criteria for inclusion and exclusion.
- Section 3 provides details on specific types of entities included in the register and on attribution criteria.
- Section 4 deals with linkages between entities.
- Section 5 discusses demography and how it is handled in the register.
- Section 6 introduces the indicators of research output provided within OrgReg.
- Section 7 presents the register’s structure and content.
- Section 8 presents the technical structure of the register and its user interface.
- Section 9 explains the procedures for maintenance and updating.

2 Definitions

The construction of a register requires dealing with three main questions:

- To define which entities should be included in the register.
- To identify the main types of entities to be covered.
- To introduce rules for inclusion and exclusion, in particular to deal with borderline cases in terms of activities and size.

This section provides some general guidelines on these three issues, which are then further detailed in the following sections.

For an in-depth discussion of the main conceptual and methodological issues around OrgReg, the reader should refer to the following paper:

Lepori B. (2020), A register of public-sector research organizations as a tool for research policy studies and evaluation, Research Evaluation, forthcoming.

2.1 Organizations

Organizations are the main type of entity covered by OrgReg. As a general rule, OrgReg aims at providing an extensive coverage at this level, while the coverage will be highly selective for organizational groups and, especially, components.

We conceptualize “organizations” as “ a collective entity with a relatively identifiable boundary, a normative order, ranks of authority, communications systems and membership coordinating systems, that exist on a relatively continues basis and it is engaged in activities that are usually related with a set of organizational goals”. The type of activities that define the core of the business of the organizations should be related to research and technological development (R&D) and/or to higher education. This concept is similar to the one of “institutional units” in the FM2015.

Following qualifications apply to this definition:

- Organizations in OrgReg are not necessarily independent legal entities, as some of them might be legally part of the public administration (but enjoying of some level of independence). However, a key criterion is that the organizations in OrgReg enjoy of some level of independence in the conduct of R&D and/or higher education, for example concerning the allocation of financial resources and the management of R&D projects (FM2015, section 3.5).
- Since research and higher education organizations are generally decentralized entities, where components enjoy of substantial autonomy, the identification of the correct disaggregation level might prove to be problematic. As a general rule, OrgReg includes only the whole entity, like a higher education institution and a whole Public Research Organization, the main criterions being the existence of a hierarchical structure where the organizational management decides on some key processes for the organization (particularly concerning the budget).
- On the contrary, organizations controlled by other organizations (for example research centres controlled by a university, but managed independently) are included as individual organizations (while the control linkages are recorded separately in the linkage table).

Remark: while the concept of *organization* is similar to the one of the *enterprise* in the Business Unit Register, a major difference between the two is that in OrgReg organizations are considered as entities in the real world, while in the BUR enterprises are purely statistical constructs built

by grouping legal units. An important implication is that organizations can be linked in OrgReg (while enterprises are not linked in the BUR).

2.2 Delimitation of the register

In general, the register includes organizations which have a sizeable level of R&D and/or higher education activities and which belong to the broader public sector, including also public non-profit organizations.

More precisely, following general criteria apply to identify the organizations to be included in OrgReg:

a) R&D and/or higher education should be part of the organizational mission or major activity of the concerned organizations. Entities for which research and tertiary education are only accessory activities at the service of their main mission are in principle excluded, with the relevant exception of healthcare providers, which perform a significant level of R&D or clinical research.

Specifically, following categories of organizations are excluded:

- Organizations in charge of technology transfer and service without a specific R&D mission (for example technology transfer centres).
- Units within public administration with a political and/or service role and performing some R&D only as a support for these tasks. On the contrary, research entities within the public administration are included.

b) The register includes public-sector organizations, defined as those organizations having a public mission and/or mandate to perform research and tertiary education activities. It also covers Private Non-Profit Organizations performing research and/or tertiary education without an immediate for-profit goal – even if part of their revenues are generated by selling services. Therefore, the register coverage broadly corresponds to the aggregation of the higher education, government and private non-profit sector of the Frascati Manual.

The register excludes organizations, for which R&D and education are performed mainly to support the market of enterprises, like an internal research center of a pharmaceutical company. Such entities will be dealt separately in the enterprise organizational register. Conforming to the FM, this applies also to public corporations, i.e. business enterprises for which the majority of the shares is owned by the government (service utilities for example), the basic criterion being market orientation rather than ownership. Following the FM, private higher education institutions are included as part of the higher education sector.

Public-private partnerships that support private companies in their innovation activities are included even if they are largely market-oriented at the following conditions:

- There is a public mandate for this activity (even if most revenues are generated from market activities).
- The partnership includes also public actors.
- Some funds are non-commercial.

R&D and innovation support units that are fully in the private sector (like those managed by professional associations in their own) are excluded.

c) The organizations included in the register should reach a sizeable amount of R&D and/or tertiary education activities. This criterion aims to focus the register on organizations, which are a stable part of the R&D and higher education system, and which account for a sizeable part of its activities. It aims also to limit the number of organizations included and therefore to keep the register manageable.

Specifically, it is suggested that organizations are included in the register when they reach at least one of the following thresholds:

- At least 30 FTE of R&D or higher education personnel (as an average of the period 2011-2015).
- At least 100 tertiary education students (as an average of the period 2011-2015).
- At least 50 publications in the Web of Science database in the period 2011-2015.
- At least 10 EU Framework Programs projects (all FP included).
- At least 5 patents in a five-year period (2011-2015).
- For Research Funding Organizations (RFOs) and charities at least 10m Euros funding (as an average of the period 2011-2015).

It is meant that these criteria should be considered over a 3-5 years period, meaning that organizations approaching this threshold over such a period should be included. Transient organizations matching the criteria only in a single year should be generally excluded.

These thresholds are meant as a guidance for inclusion/exclusion decisions. National experts compiling the register might decide exceptions based on specific criteria, like national visibility.

d) Following types of organizations are generally excluded from the register:

- Policy think tanks.
- Science museums and organizations in charge of the dialogue between science and society, except when they have an explicit research mission.
- Public-private cooperation entities with no R&D mission and outputs, like pure technology transfer centres, technology parks, etc., except when they have an explicit research mission.
- Professional associations and technical centres providing on-pay services to companies (without a prevalent public mission).
- Virtual centres or laboratories, as a joint venture between different research organization having mostly a coordinating role, but not their own staff and research facilities.

Exceptions might be decided by national experts based on the extent of R&D activity and national visibility.

2.3 Levels of entities

The main focus of the register will be on organizations, as defined in section 2.1. However, following the practice of the Business Units Register (BUR), OrgReg distinguishes following additional levels of entities:

- Groups of organizations.
- Organizational components.
- Local establishments.
- Consortia of organizations.

The register will provide some coverage of groups of organizations and of consortia, as these are relevant to identify ties between organizations; coverage of organizational components will be selective, while local establishment will be covered only through their locations.

2.3.1 Groups of organizations

By definition, *groups of organizations* are sets of organizations, which are bound together by legal or financial links, similar to groups of enterprises in the BUR. Such links might include:

- A legal framework where the higher level entity (the “group”) is delegated some key decision-making processes, like the definition of strategic priorities and allocation of resources (while partner organizations maintain their own independence).
- Financial control or ownership of partner organizations.
- Indirect control for example through the right of nominating all members of the organizational board.
- A state decision to “group” organizations in a single setting endowing the group head of some important decisions on the member organizations, including the management of the state contribution to the participating organizations.

Example: The French Communities of Universities (COMUE) are recognized as part of the French higher education system and enrol the graduate students of their partner universities. Therefore, they will be integrated in the register as groups of organizations. On the contrary, university associations like the Russel group in the UK will not be included, as they are just loosely coupled entities.

The distinction between organizations and organizational groups might be in some cases difficult to establish. As a general rule, organizations have some kind of internal hierarchy and a central budget, where the organizational centres can take important decisions concerning the components. On the contrary, organizational groups are based on a more distributed setting, where constitutive organizations keep their independence, but pool some of their activities and resources based on a specific agreement, respectively, some high-level strategic decisions are concentrated in the hands of group.

Example: the Helmholtz Association was created in 1995 as a formal head of the 18 Helmholtz centres; the association has therefore a legal status independent of its members, distributes core funding to the centres and evaluates them. The centres however remain autonomous and independent in their management and research activity. It will be therefore included as a group of organizations.

In the case of a group, OrgReg will include both the high-level entity (the “group head”) as a distinct entity and the participating organizations as individual entities; the relationships between them will be coded through a specific linkage (see further in section 4). However, there might be some exceptions where the group-only entity is included when data are difficult to reconstruct for the partner organizations.

2.3.2 Consortia of organizations

Consortia of organizations are entities jointly created by a number of organizations in order to perform some common tasks, particularly coordinating their activities in some areas of R&D and/or of education (for HEIs).

- Unlike groups, there is no top-down relationships of control between the group and the participating organizations.
- Unlike controlled research organizations and joint components, consortia have mostly a coordinating function between the partner organizations, rather than to conduct R&D on their own. Therefore, consortia have to be distinguished from entities created by groups of organizations to perform joint research.
- Unlike strategic alliances (not covered by OrgReg), consortia have a clear legal framework and are intended to be lasting; frequently, they will have an official public recognition of their coordinating function.

This category is meant to include selectively some important entities, which would not fit into other types of entities covered by OrgReg. A central inclusion criterion is their recognition by the national state as having a coordination function within the national research and higher education system, like in the case of the Italian Interuniversity consortia (for example National Interuniversity Consortium of Materials Science and Technology). Purely bottom-up consortia created by research organizations should be in principle excluded.

Consortia are attributed to entity types depending on the entities which belong to them: therefore, a national consortium including PROs and HEIs will be attributed to both types. As a general rule, linkages between consortia and participating entities are not tracked in OrgReg.

2.3.3 Organizational components

Organizational components refer to part of organizations which are focused on specific topics or subject domains, respectively might enjoy of a large autonomy in the decision-making, but are not independent organizations. Typical examples of organizational components are Faculties or Departments in higher education institutions, laboratories in large PROs like CNRS, hospitals belonging to other research or higher education institutions.

Organizational components are part of the hierarchical structure of the organization they belong and clearly identified as a part of the organization (for example a faculty belonging to a university). Usually, they don't have a separate budget and personnel. Therefore, components must be distinguished from controlled organizations, which are autonomous in their management and administration. Organizational components are the analogous of plants or divisions of firms in the firms register, which must be distinguished from subsidiaries, which are independent organizations on their own.

OrgReg does not intend to provide a comprehensive coverage of organizational components. **The general rule is that components should be included if they have visibility as an entity in their own, even if they belong to larger entities.** Specifically, this includes following cases:

- Hospitals which are components to universities (in order to avoid comparability issues due to the different position of hospitals in respect to universities; see further section 3.4).
- Types of organizations that might occupy different positions (for example some of them being components, other affiliated organizations, like in the case of the French observatories).
- Components established in a different country than the parent organization (like the Max Planck Institute in the Netherlands or the individual institutes of the European Commission Joint Research Centres).
- Joint components, when they are of very large size and have their own visibility.
- **Components that are visible as individual entities on their own, like large national facilities hosted by universities, or schools, which pre-existed a merger and are still mostly recognized with their own identity.**

OrgReg does not generally include components of HEIs such as faculties or departments, as well as laboratories within larger research organizations.

Remark: components need to be distinguished from affiliated organizations. The former are part of the organizational hierarchy and directly subject to (some level of) central steering, while affiliated organizations might be characterized by control (for example the main organization nominating the board of trustees members) and have strong functional integration, but are still independent in their decision and making and conduct. In most cases, affiliated organizations hire directly their personnel and have a distinct budget from the main organization.

2.3.4 Local establishments

By definition, *local establishments* are parts of an organization situated in a specific geographic place. These include for example a campus of a university in another city than the main seat or a laboratory of a large public research organization in a different place than its headquarters, a very frequent occurrence for large so-called Umbrella organizations like CNRS. Local establishments usually correspond to distinct organizational components (but more components might be included in the same local establishment).

The register will not single out local establishments individually, as this would be too resource-consuming. However, it will include a specific location table, where the individual locations of each organization covered by the registered are listed with their geographical coordinates and time-spam (see section 7.5).

2.4 Relationships with the firms register (FirmReg)

Within the RISIS project, a parallel work is developing a prototype of a firms register (FirmReg). The firms register will be very similar to OrgReg in its basic structure and variables, but with some key differences related to the specific nature of firms; these are:

- FirmReg will be cross-sectional as following the firms' demography would be complex and time-consuming.
- FirmReg will be selective in tracking linkages between entities and mainly cover linkages of the included entities with their Global Ultimate Owner (GUO).
- The perimeter of FirmReg will be first defined by the firms included in the three RISIS firms database, i.e. CIB, Cheetah and VICO.

In general terms, the divide between OrgReg and FirmReg is very similar to the one between the business sector and the HEI, Government and PNP sector in the Frascati manual, i.e. entities with a prevalent market orientation will be excluded from OrgReg (see further in section 3) and, in future, should be included in FirmReg. The exception are public-private partnerships (like technological centres) that are included in OrgReg despite their mixed character.

2.5 Coverage

2.5.1 Temporal coverage and update

The temporal coverage of the register is from 2000 to the most recent year. This means that all entities fulfilling inclusion criteria that existed after 2000 are included (even if they were closed in the meantime) and following events are tracked from 2000 onwards:

- Demographic events.
- Changes in names and characteristics.
- Changes in locations.
- Changes in linkages.

OrgReg is updated continuously based on information provided by partners, for example new entries in linked datasets. As a general rule, an annual revision of the whole register is performed. Specifically checking for any changes in the recorded units (e.g. from their respective websites).

2.5.2 Geographical coverage

The register covers EU-27, EFTA (Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway and Switzerland), the UK, EU-candidate countries and potential candidate countries (Albania, Bosnia-Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Kosovo, Montenegro, Serbia and Turkey) and Israel.

Relevant international agencies and performers, based on international agreements or within the European Union framework, are also included; examples are ESO, CERN, the Joint research Centre of the European Commission. These entities are coded as 'INT' while their specific location (for example Switzerland for CERN) is entered in the location table.

3 Types of entities

The definition of types of entities is important to structure the register, but also because slightly different rules for inclusion and exclusion might apply for each type. OrgReg includes the following types of organizations:

- Higher Education Institutions (HEI), which deliver education at the tertiary level (in practice at the least at the bachelor level) and, possibly, research activities. They might be public and private (see below section 3.2).
- Public Research Organizations (PRO), mostly performing R&D activities, possibly together with some services, including the large national umbrella organizations like CNRS and MPG (see section 3.3).
- Public Administration Organizations (PA), i.e. parts of the public administration, which perform a sizeable volume of R&D, but are functionally integrated within the public administration structure (see section 3.4).
- Research Hospitals (RH), i.e. medical care organizations which perform a sizeable amount of R&D or clinical research, independently from the fact they are linked or not to a university (see section 3.5).
- Private Non-profit Organizations (PNP), which are part of the private sector, but are not primarily oriented to the market (see section 3.6).
- Research Funding Organizations distributing public project funding (see section 3.7).
- Charities, i.e. private non-profit entities providing project funds on a non-exchange basis (see section 3.8).

As presented in Table 1, there is a general correspondence between the OrgReg types and the Frascati Manual sector. OrgReg provides a more fine-grained division of entities in the government sector depending on their level of functional independence (PA vs. PRO type) and singling out medical care entities. A relevant difference is that OrgReg focuses on entity characteristics and not only on control: therefore, large research centres which are controlled by HEIs will be categorized as PROs, while in the FM classification they belong to the HE sector (the dependency relationship being handled through a linkage). A second difference is that the coverage of higher education is more extensive, as OrgReg includes also HEIs not having a sizeable volume of R&D, but providing only education.

Table 1. Correspondence between Frascati Manual sectors and OrgReg types

FM sector	Higher Education	Government	Private non Profit	Business Enterprise
OrgReg types	HEIs	PRO, PA, RH	PNP	Excluded
Remarks	HEIs in OrgReg include also entities which do not perform R&D.	Some of these entities might be included in the FM HEI sector depending on their functional dependency.		In both cases, public corporations are in this sector.

3.1 Attribution to types

The attribution to types is based on fulfilling a set of criteria as spelled out in Table 2. More detail on the specific criteria for each type are provided in the sections below.

Table 2. Criteria for attributing entities to types

Type	Criteria (AND)
HEI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delivering degrees at tertiary level (ISCED levels 5 to 8).
PROs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R&D as the main mission of the entity. Part of the public sector (public mission, no exclusive market orientation). Functional independence from the state in the conduct of R&D.
Public administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public administration with no substantive independence Policy or service mission. R&D as a collateral mission or sizeable volume of R&D
RH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Medical care as the main mission. Sizeable volume of R&D or clinical research.
PNP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R&D as the main mission. No government control. No exclusive market orientation.
RTO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public mission of transferring research results. Public actors in the partnership. Not fully market-oriented.
RFOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public agencies with some independence in the attribution of grants Project funding as a regular activity. Funds coming mostly from the government.
Charities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project funding as a regular activity. Mostly supporting public science. Most funds from private donors.

Remarks:

a) While in OrgReg types will mostly apply to the organizational level, the classification by level and type are conceptually independent – for example it is possible that an HEI (organizational level) has a PRO as a component.

b) In most cases, OrgReg entities will be attributed to a single type, but multiple types are possible when entities fulfil all the corresponding criteria.

For example, the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences is coded as a PRO (public-sector, main mission R&D), but also to the HEI sector, as it delivers a sizeable number of PhD degrees.

As a rule, multiple attributions should be based on substantive criteria, for example a sizeable number of higher education degrees.

c) Entities not fulfilling any of these set of criteria – and therefore not attributed to a type – should be excluded from OrgReg (as these criteria operationalize the broad delimitation in section 2.2).

3.2 Higher Education Institutions

Definitions and delimitation for Higher Education Institutions are based on the European Tertiary Education Register (ETER; www.eter-project.com). The HEI definition in the register will be therefore identical with the one of ETER and OrgReg will include all HEIs in ETER using the same codes. However, OrgReg might also include some additional HEIs, for example institutions closed before 2008 (the EUMIDA reference year).

ETER defines Higher Education Institutions as entities:

- which are recognizable as distinct organizations,
- which are nationally recognized as HEIs, and
- whose major activity is providing education at the tertiary level (ISCED 2011 level 5, 6, 7 and/or 8). R&D activities might be present, but are not a necessary condition for inclusion in the perimeter. De facto, ETER has a full coverage from level ISCED 6 (including vocational education), but largely excludes HEIs delivering only ISCED 5 level diplomas.

An HEI is nationally recognized, if it is officially accredited as such by a legitimate organization in a country. Recognizable as a distinct organization means that the perimeter of these institutions can be identified rather unambiguously, they have an internal organizational structure and, at least in principle, their own budget.

To operationalize this definition, the following criteria are used:

- *Main activity*. Institutions for which education at ISCED 2011 level 5, 6, 7 and/or 8 (former ISCED 97 level 5 and/or 6) is a major activity and constitutive part of their mission. These institutions can have a large share of research activity, but it should not be their only purpose. In practical terms, this means that a substantial share of staff time is devoted to education.
- *Graduation at ISCED 2011 level 5, 6, 7 and/or 8*. In principle, institutions delivering courses in curricula, where the degree is attributed by other institutions are excluded.
- *National recognition as higher education institutions*, for example in national laws, is a relevant criterion of inclusion. This might include the specific mention of the institution in the law ruling higher education, accreditation by a specific body, and mention in the list of official recognized HEIs.
- *Size and visibility* is a further criterion, also for practical purposes. Size should be measured by staff data and number of students enrolled as a reference. As a general rule, institutions with less than 30 FTEs of academic staff and less than 200 students should be included only in exceptional cases, specifically for institutions mostly awarding degrees at ISCED level 8.
- *Continuity*, hence the intention of being a stable organization, is another delimitation criteria. Thus, structures which are in principle transitory, for example for offering just one training cycle, should not be included in the perimeter.

Examples of higher education institutions to be included are universities (PhD awarding), as well as universities of applied sciences (Fachhochschulen, Polytechnics). Other examples are Colleges of Arts and Music, theological schools, schools of pedagogy and distance education universities. Institutions offering only services for education (but no curricula) are not included in the ETER data collection despite their inclusion in the UOE data collection (non-instructional institutions; see UOE handbook 4.3.2).

Research institutions, like public research institutes and Academies of Sciences, whose principal mandate is performing R&D, are not included in HE (on the basis of the main activity criterion) even if they are delivering some educational activities, except they deliver a large number of doctoral degrees. The same applies for organizations providing other types of professional services, which offer training courses as a side activity.

3.3 Public Research Organizations

Public Research Organizations are defined as entities whose main activity is to carry out Research and Development (R&D), according to the Frascati Manual definition.

PRO need to have at least one of the following features to be considered as such:

- Have the legal status of public organization or be publicly owned by the Government (i.e. created by a political process).
- Be publicly funded on a regular basis, receive significant parts of its budget from the Government; or the Government could have a say in the appointment of its Managers.
- Be in charge, on behalf of the Government, of developing a public mission or of providing public goods related to its main R&D activities; or be created as a result of a Government initiative or policy program.
- PROs have to be capable of decision making with respect to the conduct of R&D, from the allocation of financial resources for internal or external use, to the management of R&D projects. Entities performing on behalf and under the direct conduct of politics will be classified as PA.

Remarks and delimitation with other organization categories

a) Organizations for which a major activity is tertiary education are included in OrgReg as Higher Education Institutions. This also includes graduate education, for example graduate schools. The main delimitation criterion is the degree: therefore, public research organizations who host PhD students as researchers, but the degree is awarded by a university are categorized under PROs. Some special cases, like the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, which are traditional PROs, but award a large number of PhD degrees, will be attributed to both types of organizations.

b) Healthcare organizations with a large R&D component are classified in the category "Research hospitals". Research centres in medicine without an educational and healthcare component under the category PRO.

c) The PRO perimeter excludes companies whose main mission is to sell for profit goods or services, including public-sector companies as well (railways, telecommunications). Equally excluded are private research centres selling R&D services to third-parties even if they have an independent legal status (for example as a private foundation). The latter are included in the private non-profit category.

However, entities with a private legal status are included in OrgReg as PROs in the following cases:

- When they are mostly funded through public money.

- When, they are in charge of a policy mission and have been created through a policy process, even if they are mostly funded by selling services

The most relevant example for the latter case are Research Technology Organizations or Technology Centres, whose main mission is to support the transfer of results of public research to the private sector; they are included in OrgReg even if their main source of revenues are service charges and technological licenses, at the condition they also perform a sizeable volume of R&D.

d) Units within the public administration with a policy or service mission – for example departments of ministries or national services like metrology or weather forecast services– are selectively included under the “public administration” category (see section 3.5).

Identification of the organizational level

The identification of the organizational level might be more complex for PROs than for other types of public research organizations due to the variety of organizational structures. This issues of particularly complex for so-called large “umbrella” organizations which group a large number of labs, usually in different locations, like CNRS in France, CSIC in Spain, MPG and the Leibniz Association in Germany.

Two basic organizational models can be distinguished, which are treated differently in OrgReg (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Organizational models of PROs

Source: RISIS, WP23

The holding model is characterized by a central hierarchical structure, where the central level distributes the budget of the components, can take decisions on foundation, closure and merger of components and, in most cases, also manages internal careers and hire staff (where mobility of employees between components is in principle possible). This models is represented by cases

like CNR, CSIC or CNRS. In OrgReg, only the whole organization is included at the organizational level, while local establishments are tracked in a specific location table. OrgReg does not aim in principle to include a list of components.

In the Associated model, individual units are in principle responsible of their own decision, manage their budget and personnel; the higher level structure might work either as a common brand, like in the case of Leibnitz Association, or as a funding agency, like in the case of laboratories grouped under the heading of the Norwegian Research Council. In this model, units are included individually as organizations, while the overreaching structure is treated as a group and the corresponding linkages are tracked in the specific table. In such cases, it is however exceptionally possible that only the organization group is included, but not the participating organizations.

In practice, an important marker of this distinction is whether the affiliated institutes have their own visibility in the data sources and, particularly, in PATSTAT (as PATSTAT is based on legal owners).

3.4 Research Hospitals

Research hospitals are hospitals which, alongside their clinical activity, perform a sizeable amount of medical research; many research hospitals are also closely associated with universities and, therefore, are involved to some extent in teaching.

Therefore, the main delimitation criterion is that research hospitals should have a sizeable number of scientific publications which can be retrieved from publication databases. In practice, this implies that basic the list of such hospitals in OrgReg is retrieved from CWTS Leiden ranking database, but the list might be integrated by national experts.

Research hospitals can have different positions in respect to universities; available options are:

- Fully independent research hospitals, with no direct linkages with a university. They are entered in OrgReg as independent organizations.
- Associated hospitals (entity=organization, linkage type=association). These hospitals are typically involved in the undergraduate education activities of the medical schools but are governed by independent boards, are located in different buildings and the staff of faculty departments and hospitals clinics are quite distinct from one another. They are entered as organizations, but associated to the university.
- Affiliated hospitals (entity=organization, linkage type=affiliated). These are hospitals that are separate institutions but that are tightly integrated with the medical faculty/school which emerges from both physical integration (faculty departments located in the hospital) as well as overlap of staff.
- Component hospitals: these hospitals are considered as a component of the university and therefore defined as entity “component” affiliated to a parent organization (entity type=component; linkage type=“part of”).

Figure 2 displays the flowchart and the decision-criteria to distinguish between the different cases.

Figure 2. Flowchart for the position of research hospitals

Source CWTS

NO = can also refer to no information available

1. Legal status

- The hospital falls under the university's administration = component.
- The hospital is managed by a foundation from the university = component.
- The hospital has an autonomous legal status = move to step 2.

2. Shared mandate (core curriculum)¹

- The hospital and the university share an education (not training) **and** research mandate by the government or a foundation = component. The educational component must be targeted to university students and be part of the core curriculum. Training for professionals and outreach activities for the general public are not considered as university education.
- The hospital only shares a care and training mandate with the university = move to step 3.

3. Integration medical faculty

- The hospital's staff is paid by the university or holds a teaching/research position at the university (and vice versa) = component.
- Publications assignment. If publications authored by hospital staff are assigned to the university = component. But also, if publications are assigned to both.
- The medical faculty, or part of it, is located in the hospital premises = component.
- The hospital staff is not part of the university nor are there shared premises = associate.

The structure of OrgReg allows research hospitals to change their position in respect to universities without changing their identity (for example keeping their identifier); for example, an hospital which used to be simply associated with a university can become a component of it,

¹ This is difficult to establish but on the occasions that the lesson plan is listed on the medical faculty's website it is easy to find out if core curriculum classes are given at the hospital.

for example through a more structured cooperation agreement and stronger integration with the university medical faculty.

3.5 Public administration entities (PA)

The register will selectively include public administration services which perform a sizeable volume of R&D including:

- Entities with mostly a public service function (metrology, weather services, etc.).
- IT services.
- Ministries and departments of public administration which perform some research on their own.

The distinguishing characteristics of such entities are that a) in most cases they are not independent, but subject to direct hierarchical control from the public administration and b) research is done as a support for their main activity, but not as a goal in itself.

Inclusion of such entities is selective, based on decisions of national experts. This type should be therefore considered as a residual of which don't fit into the PRO categories for the two criteria of the R&D mission and of the independence from the public administration.

Main criteria for inclusion are:

- Research is a continuing part of the entity activities, for example it is part of their mission and can be identified on the entity website.
- The entity has a sizeable number of research projects or publications or patents.
- The entity has an identifiable research unit/group (for example clearly visible on the website).

Parts of the public administration performing R&D only sporadically as a direct service to their main mission are excluded.

Public administration entities should be included at the level of the R&D performing unit (for example the specific centre or department) and not of the larger governmental body, like the ministry or the whole country. As a general rule, these entities will be classified as components.

3.6 Private Non Profit performing organizations (PNP)

OrgReg also includes also private non-profit organization with a research mission and a sizeable research output. These entities are part of the private sector in the sense that they are not controlled or mostly financed by a state direct allocation, but their R&D is not oriented mostly to serve customer's needs. The main examples are R&D centres managed by charities or private foundations without direct commercial aim; strong linkages with companies might be present (non-profit research foundations created by the private sector), but such centres to not serve directly the company market needs.

Examples of the first type are the Institut Pasteur in France (Non-governmental organization) and Friedrich Miescher Institut in Switzerland (private foundation).

Following Frascati manual (FM2015, chapter 10), identification of this type of entities is based on the two criteria of control and market orientation: PNP are defined as entities which do not have a public mission and which do not have purely a market (customer) orientation.

Therefore:

- Entities with an explicit public mission (like many technology transfer centres) should be included in the PRO type irrespectively of their legal form. This also applies to entities whose core funding is mostly from the State (but not to entities which receive funds from the State from competitive means).

- Entities controlled by firms should be excluded and covered to the firms register.
- Entities which primarily serve customer's needs should be excluded (included mostly in firms): example are consultancies. Some PNP might receive a substantial share of their budget from fees, but market should not be their primary orientation.

3.7 Research Funding Organizations

Research Funding Organizations (RFOs) are public-sector entities that distribute public project funds to R&D performers.

Project funding is defined as money attributed to a group or an individual to perform a research activity limited in scope, budget and time. It can be identified and distinguished from institutional funding based on three main characteristics: a) funds are attributed directly to research groups and not to a whole organization b) they are limited in the scope of the research supported and its duration and c) they are attributed by a research funding organization outside the performing organization to which the beneficiary belongs (Lepori, van den Besselaar, Dinges, et al 2007).

RFOs are identified by their function, i.e. distributing public project funding, not by their legal status or organizational structure; RFOs therefore include both autonomous agencies, like Research Councils, and departments within the public administration managing project funds.

RFOs are subject to the following inclusion criteria:

- They are managing and distribution public project funding.
- The funding volume is sizeable (at least 10m Euros per year).
- They manage organized programs with regular calls and evaluation procedures.

Examples of RFOs are:

- (Semi)-autonomous agencies, like research councils and innovation agencies.
- Performers that attribute distribute project funds with open schemes; these will receive the RFO type in their characteristics (example: DLR in Germany).
- Ministerial units or departments that manage funding programs; these should be included at the level of the unit managing the program (not the broader state entity like a ministry). An exception may be represented by the Research ministry, which should be generally included as a whole since research funding its part of its constitutive mission.
- European and international agencies to the extent they have a stable legal existence (excluding programs like ERA-NETs).

The perimeter therefore excludes higher education funding agencies managing institutional funds, but also governmental departments that award contracts for their policy needs on an ad hoc basis, without a general aim to support research. Internal funding schemes to research organizations (that are not open to outside the organization) are also excluded even if their way of allocating resources might be similar to RFOs.

3.8 Charities

Charities are private non-profit organizations, for example foundations, that provide project funds for the general purpose of supporting research. The same criteria as for RFOs apply, additionally, R&D support from charities should not be market oriented, i.e. aimed to pursue the commercial goal of the funder, but support research that is generally public-domain. Charities therefore exclude research centres of companies that manage contractual research for the company's commercial goals.

Charities are subject to the following inclusion criteria:

- The funding volume is sizeable (at least 10m Euros per year).
- They manage organized programs with regular calls and evaluation procedures.
- Most of the funding comes from private donors.
- Funding is directed to public science (i.e. the entity is not simply awarding contract research on behalf of a company).

3.9 Research Technology Organizations (RTOs)

Research Technology Organizations are mainly dedicated to the development and transfer of science and technology to the private sector and society; although some of them are owned by government, in general, the administrative links of RTOs with governments tend to be looser than the rest. RTOs, often in the semi-public sphere and in the non-profit sector.

RTOs are included in OrgReg even if they are largely market-oriented at the following conditions:

1. First, they are not solely market-oriented. Solely market-oriented entities are managed by FirmReg (if they fulfil the inclusion criteria).
2. Second, they have a sizeable R&D output in terms of publications, projects or patents.
3. Third, they have a public mission to transfer research results to the private sector.
4. Forth, they include public entities like ministries and universities in their partnership.

Pure commercial entities and entities fully managed by the private sector (for example by professional organizations) are excluded.

4 Linkages between entities

While the register focuses on the identification of independent organizations, it also keeps track of the most important linkages, i.e. those having a structural and lasting character and a deep impact on the entity's activities. The coverage of linkages in the register is therefore selective and focused on the structural linkages, which are lasting and have a deep impact of R&D activities of the concerned entities.

More loose linkages like strategic alliances and co-funding of other organizations are in principle excluded.

Linkages might be ordered (i.e. with a specific direction of the linkages), like membership, or non-ordered, i.e. where there is no specific direction and the partner entities have the same respective position, like in the case of the presence of a joint unit between two organizations.

OrgReg distinguishes two basic types of linkages:

a) *Membership* is a vertical linkage where an entity of lower level is part of an entity of higher level. This includes the three following cases:

- A component, which is part of an organization.
- An organization, which is controlled by a group.
- An organization, which is member of a consortium.

Since these three types of linkages are distinguished by the level of the involved entities, they are coded in the same way for sake of simplicity.

b) Horizontal linkages between different organizations. OrgReg distinguishes between three types of horizontal linkages, based on their structural characteristics.

Affiliated (ordered) is a strong structural relationships between two organizations. This might include different situations, the list below being not necessarily exhaustive:

- Organizational control, is a relationship where an organization de facto has control on the general policy of another organization, which however has autonomy in the conduct of its operations. Following the Business Unit Register, control can be operationalized with following criteria:
 - Direct hierarchical control like in the public administration.
 - Control through the nomination of the majority of the board, of the CEO, etc.
 - Control through ownership of the majority of the shares.
- Cases where one of the two organizations shares with the other some essential elements concerning R&D and educational activities, like facilities, educational programs, research staff. The main example are university hospitals, which are de facto closely integrated with a university and, for example, are clearly labelled as the "hospital of university X", while being formally independent (see section 3.4).

Association (non-ordered) is a structural and lasting relationship between two entities, where the level of integration is less strong than affiliated. The main case currently recorded in the register is a Hospital which is independent, but which offers routinely study places to medicine students and where a part of the hospital staff also holds an academic position. This structural element differentiates association from other forms of more loose cooperation, like strategic alliances. Association is possible also between entities at different levels (between a group and an organization).

Joint unit (non-ordered) characterizes the special case where two entities share one component, like in the case of joint units between universities and PROs. Given its importance, this form of

association is singled out as a specific category. The joint unit linkages is between two entities at the same level and, usually, the component is not included in the register. In case it is included, the membership relationships will be coded separately.

Cases where a joint unit is an independent organization affiliated to two other organizations and included in the register are coded through the “affiliated” linkages of both organizations. The definition of joint unit is restrictive, in the sense that it implies a structural form of relationships and the fact that joint unit a sizeable size and it is divided between the parent organizations in terms of staff and budget, while having a single label. Therefore, forms of association where a unit situated within an organization is labelled as joint with another organization (but funds and personnel are wholly managed by the form) should not be included.

Figure 3. Types of linkages in the register

Linkages are recorded in a separate table in the register that will also include start and end date of the register and some basic characterization of the type of linkage. The register will not however include quantitative information, for example on the split of human resources of joint labs, as the goal is solely to inform on the presence of the linkage.

Given the fact that linkages might evolve over time, all information on linkages in OrgReg is time-stamped (i.e. includes a start and end date of the linkage).

5 Demographic events

Demographic events are occurrences, which involve a change in the basic organizational units included in the register: examples of demographic events are the birth of an organization, its closure, the merger between two organizations which gives rise to a new organization, etc.

Demographic events do not include transformations of an organization which do not alter its identity, like the change of the name, relocation or the opening or closure of activities. They also do not include transformation in legal status of existing organizations, for example as an outcome of legal reforms, when organizations keep their continuity.

Therefore, the register will cover two types of changes:

- Demographic events which imply a discontinuity in the considered entity. These are recorded through changes in IDs.
- Changes in other characteristics of the entity, which keeps the same identity. Those characteristics only which are central for identifying the entity and matching with other databases – particularly the name and location of the organization – are recorded on an annual basis in the register. Other characteristics might be recorded, again on an annual basis, within sub-registers dedicated to individual organization types.

In some cases it might be difficult to decide whether an event represents just a change of an existing organization or the closure of one organization and the foundation of another one.

In general, the main criteria to distinguish an organizational change from a demographic event should be the following;

- Continuity in the management and organizational structure.
- Continuity in the main activities and production factors (for example personnel).
- Continuity in location.
- Continuity in the name and official recognition.

When most of these characteristics change, an entity should be subject to a demographic event (for example closure and birth of a new entity). The establishment of a new legal entity might be an indication of a demographic events, but there are cases where it should be considered as an organizational change – for example the transformation of a PRO in a private legal entity while keeping its mission, funding source and activities does not constitute a demographic event.

Following are examples of cases which should *not* be considered as demographic events:

- Changes in the name when the entity keeps most of its activities and employees
- Extension of activities and/or opening of new locations, like new educational offerings, the opening of new research centres and new campuses.
- Changes in legal status when keeping activities and structure, like the recognition of colleges as universities (even if accompanied by a change in name).

Demographic events in OrgReg can be divided in the following groups:

- Those events which imply the creation of entities (foundation) or the closure of existing entities (closure). Since they are unique to each entity, they are handled directly by attributing the corresponding foundation and closure years.
- Those events which imply the grouping of entities (mergers) or their division (split). They are recorded as separate events, while the involved entities receive the corresponding foundation and closure years.

- Those events which imply the change of relationships between entities, in most cases an organization becoming a component of another organization (take-over) or a component becoming independent (spin-out). They are handled as demographic events, while the involved organization disappears from the register in case of take-over (closure year at the take-over) or it is included newly from the spin-out (foundation year at the spin-out). This is consistent with the rule that, in general, components of organizations are not included in the register.

6 OrgReg indicators

Besides providing basic identification information on entities, OrgReg also provides a set of indicators at the organizational level measuring their activities and, specifically, research and technology outputs. The indicators are mostly derived from other RISIS datasets, specifically the WoS publication database at CWTS, Leiden University, the EUPRO database on participation to European Framework programs at AIT, Vienna, and the patent database derived from PATSTAT at IFRIS in Paris. The list might be expanded in future including indicators from other sources.

6.1 Indicators

Table 3 lists the indicators available in OrgReg for scientific publications, patents and European projects. Definitions and calculation methods are provided below.

Table 3. Organizational indicators

Category	Indicator	Data source
Scientific production and outreach	Number of publications	CWTS publication database
	Number of publications in the Top10% cited	
	Number of international scientific collaborations	
Technological production	Number of patent applications	RISIS patent database
	Number of transnational patent applications	
European research projects	Number of EU-FP participations	RISIS-EUPRO
	Number of EU-FP coordination	RISIS-EUPRO

All indicators refer to the calendar year and are numeric.

A data item is attributed to an organization in OrgReg when at least one address in the publication author list, in the project partner list or in the applicants' list of a patent is linked to that organization by the same OrgReg ID.

The reference to the identifier implies that attribution might depart from some organizational characteristics, for instance an item might be attributed to an entity before it existed (for example in case of mergers) or in a region where it has no official seat. Also, linked organizations are treated as in the original data items. This might impact comparability in cases of organizations with many linked entities. OrgReg provides the information on demographic events and linkages, which might affect comparability of indicators. However, data have to be cleaned case by case.

In general, full counting is adopted as the goal is to characterize the activities of individual organizations; accordingly, subtotals (for example publications by organizations) do not add to the regional or national totals. Indicators for a given geographical space are available through the RISIS-KNOWMAK tool (www.knowmak.eu).

1.1.1 Indicators on scientific production

These indicators characterize the volume of scientific output and its visibility through number of publications and of citations.

The indicators are based on CWTS in-house version of the Web of Science (WoS) database (Science Citation Index Expanded, Social Sciences Citation Index, and Arts & Humanities Citation Index) of Clarivate Analytics'. WoS is a bibliographic database that covers the publications of about 12,000 journals in the sciences, the social sciences, and the arts and humanities. Each journal in WoS is assigned to one or more subject categories. We note that CWTS in-house version of the WoS database includes a number of improvements over the original WoS database. Most importantly, CWTS database uses a more advanced citation matching algorithm.

For publications, reference year is the publication year.

Full documentation on publication indicators and additional indicators are available here: <https://rcf.risis2.eu/dataset/3/metadata>.

Variable name	Variable label	Variable description	Type
OrgReg_P	Number of publications (Web of Science)	The count of publications for a given combination of dimensions from the Thomson Reuters' Web of Science database (Science Citation Index Expanded, Social Sciences Citation Index, and Arts & Humanities Citation Index). Only publications of the Web of Science document type's <i>article</i> and <i>review</i> are considered. Only publications with at least one European address.	count
OrgReg_Ptop10%	Number of publications in the top10% cited	Count of the publications belonging to the given aggregation level that are in the top10% of their respective field. In case of ties, the publication is fractionalized.	count
OrgReg_Pint	Number of publications with international collaborations	Number of publications belonging to a given aggregation level that have at least one address in another country	count

1.1.2 Indicators of technological production

Indicators on technological production are derived from the IFRIS-PATSTAT version, which RISIS Patent offers an enriched and cleaned version of the PATSTAT database, a database of all patent offices produced by the European patent office (EPO).

For all patent indicators, the reference year is the priority year of the patent.

Full documentation on the database and additional indicators are available here: <https://rcf.risis2.eu/dataset/5/metadata>.

Variable name	Variable label	Variable description	Type
OrgReg_Pat	Number of priority patent applications	Count of the patents belonging to a given entity. Priority patents are counted, i.e. the first unique filing, which serves as the 'priority' application date for a family, e.g. when a patent is extended to other countries. Only patents with at least one European address including PATSTAT 'artificial' patents. Patents are attributed to spaces based on the inventors' addresses.	count
OrgReg_Pattrans	Number of transnational patent applications	The count of transnational priority patent applications, i.e. those priority patents that have been extended in at least another patent office.	count

1.1.3 Indicators on European research projects

Indicators for European research projects are derived from the EUPRO database. EUPRO is a unique dataset providing systematic and standardized information on R&D projects, participants and resulting networks of the EU FP, starting from FP1, and recently integrating H2020 (until 2016), and other European funding instruments, such as EUREKA, COST and selected Joint Technology Initiatives (JTIs). Basically, EUPRO covers cleaned and standardised information on R&D projects (such as project objectives and achievements, project costs, total funding, start and end date, contract type, information on the call), and their participants (standardized name of the participating organisation, organisation type, and geographical location).

For all EU-FP indicators projects are counted that are active in the reference year.

Full documentation on the database and additional indicators are available here: <https://rcf.risis2.eu/dataset/5/metadata>.

Variable name	Variable label	Variable description	Type
OrgReg_EUpart	Number of EU-FP participations	The number of EU-FP participations of the considered organization running in the reference year.	count
OrgReg_EUcord	Number of EU-FP coordinations	The number of EU-FP coordinations of the considered organization running in the reference year.	Count

6.2 Regional breakdown

Besides providing aggregated figures at the organizational level, OrgReg also provides indicators disaggregated at the regional level, by using the NUTS3 classification (2016 edition)². This feature will only be available for indicators extracted from the KNOWMAK central database.

This feature is particularly important for large PROs, such as CNRS, which have laboratories distributed throughout a whole country. Most other entities in OrgReg only have indicators in a single region. Noticeably, since the regional attribution is based on addresses, some entities might have indicators in a region where no seat is recorded in the OrgReg location table.

Data items are attributed to OrgReg entities and regions by the addresses of applicants, respectively in the project participations. Since full counting is applied, the sum of regional figures is generally larger than the aggregate, which is recorded separately in the OrgReg database.

6.3 Data integration and update

Indicators for OrgReg are produced in two different ways:

- Through direct extraction (via API) from the KNOWMAK database.
- Through direct import from data files in the OrgReg database.

The first option allows more automation and more frequent update. It also allows providing regional breakdowns for indicators. It is however conditional to the availability of data and their update in the KNOWMAK tool.

The second option might be adopted for additional indicators not available in KNOWMAK.

² <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/nuts-maps>

7 Structure and content of the register

As shown in Figure 4, the whole register infrastructure is composed by three components:

- The *core register* which stores the essential information on entity identity and demographics. The core register structure and implementation are described in detail in this handbook.
- *Organizational subregisters* by type of organizations. These subregisters include key information on the concerned organizations, like their budget, number of personnel, students (for HEIs). Subregisters are independent from the core register from a functional perspective, but share with them organizational IDs and the technical infrastructure. A first subregister which will be implemented is the European Tertiary Education Register enhanced version (including also additional data from the RISIS project, like publications and participations to EU-FP programs). Further subregisters which might be realized are include PRO and RFOs.
- Linked datasets through the use of the register IDs in their respective organizational tables. These include EUPRO, the Leiden Ranking, and IFRIS-PATSTAT. The advantage of the linkages through IDs is that there is no need to store within the register the variants of entity names specific to each database (for example the Web of Science), since this harmonization process is already dealt within each specific database.

Figure 4. General structure of the register

The core register is composed by five tables. Its central component is the **entities table**, which contains the complete list of all entities stored in the register, i.e. consortia, organizations and components, each associated with a unique ID. The choice of storing all entities in the same table allows dealing with the transformation of entities in a consistent way, for example when a component of an organization is transformed into an independent entity.

The **entities characteristics table** stores a core set of characteristics for each entity, like its legal name, the location of the main seat, the entity level and type. The fact that these characteristics are stored in a separate table, allows to track changes in these characteristics over time for the same entity by attributing to each set of characteristics a start and end date.

The **demographic events table** records all demographic events involving entities, while the **linkages table** contains all linkages between units, including their type and start and end date. Finally, the **location table** stores the spatial location of the local establishments associated with an entity.

Below, we provide a detailed description of the content of each individual table.

Remark: no name variants are stored in the register, as it is assumed that, once the register is available, variants can be extracted from open data sources or from existing datasets.

7.1 Entity table

The entity table of the register will include following variables:

- Entity_ID. A unique identifier for the entity.
- Current entity name in English.
- Current entity acronym.
- The entity foundation year (and respective remark field).
- The entity closure year (and respective remark field).
- The currently valid website (for purposes of tracking information and searching the Internet).

7.1.1 Identifiers

Identifiers are meant to uniquely identify organizations included in the register across time. This also implies that, when an organization ceases to exist, the corresponding code is not reassigned. ID will have the following format: ISO-Country code (http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-1) + 4 digits numeric (e.g. FR0001).

A specific code INT is included to track supranational organizations, including international organizations based on treaties, CERN (PRO) or the UN system agencies, as well as those organizations which are directly part of the European Union structure, like the Joint Research Center or the European Research Council.

It is envisaged to use the first numerical digit to identify the type of organization in order to simplify the management of the register and its integration with other databases:

- ID from XX0001 to XX0999 are attributed to HEIs. HEIs not belonging to ETER are attributed codes from XX0800 onwards to avoid overlaps.
- ID from XX1000 to XX1999 are attributed to PROs and RTOs.
- ID from XX2000 to XX2999 are attributed to research hospitals.
- ID from XX3000 to XX3999 are attributed to public administration organizations (PA).
- ID from XX4000 to XX4999 are attributed to private non-profit (PNP).
- ID from XX5000 to XX5999 are attributed to research funding organizations (RFO) and to charities.
- ID from XX9000 to XX9999 are attributed to other entities.

The attribution of this group of codes refers to the type of organization at the moment where an organization is inserted in the register and serves for convenience in numbering. It is possible

that for single cases it does not correspond with the types tracked in the organizational characteristics (which might change over time).

This ID format is preferred to the reuse of existing codes (like fiscal codes) since the latter do not necessarily match the needs of a register (for example concerning stability over time). The register could include information on related codes, for example from national databases.

7.1.2 Current entity name and acronym

The entity table includes the currently valid entity name and acronym in English for informative purposes, as this makes easier to users to manage the data. If there is no English name, the name in the national language should be used.

The current name must be identical to name in English entered into the entity-characteristics table for the currently valid set of characteristics (i.e. the characteristics with no end date, end date variable equal to “a”). If there is no English name, the legal name will be used.

These variables will be updated automatically within the database from the entity characteristics table in order to be up to date and avoid any inconsistencies.

7.1.3 Foundation and closure years

The identifier table of the register includes the following information:

- The **foundation year**, defined as the *first year* when the entity first existed (corresponding to a birth in demography). This event is associated to the assignment of a unique ID in the register.
- The **closure year**, defined as the *last year* when the entity existed and, therefore, for the following years the unique ID is not any more valid for assigning characteristics to entity.

Foundation and closure have to be distinguished from other entity changes, like the change in legal status or dependency relationships (like a hospitals becoming independent from a university) or changes of name. At the same time, the foundation year should be the first year where the entity existed in its current structure and activities. It is recognized that many entities might have an ancestor, for example a specialized school which was transformed into a generalist university with a new mission, organization structure and personnel. Generally, it is not the purpose of the register to track the detailed history of entities and this variable should just be informative on the presence of entities of time.

A number of demographic events imply the foundation of new entities (mergers, spin-outs) or the closure of some entities (mergers, take-over). Therefore, consistency rules between demographic events and foundation and closure year apply.

7.1.4 Variables

- Entity_ID. Format: text, 6 digits (two digits ISO country code and four numerical digits).
- Entity current name. Format: text. Updated automatically from the entity characteristics table.
- Entity current acronym. Format: text. Updated automatically from the entity characteristics table.
- Entity foundation year. Numeric, 4 digits.
- Entity foundation remarks. Text.
- Entity closure year. Numeric, 4 digits.
- Entity closure remarks. Text.
- Website of entity (text).

7.1.5 Special codes:

- When foundation year is not known, code “m” (missing) is attributed. This is interpreted in any case as meaning that the entity existed already in the year 2000 (start year of tracking demographic events).
- Code “m” is not allowed for the closure year.
- When the entity is still existing at last year of update of the register, code “a” (not applicable).
- When the entity has been closed (closure year code different from “a”) and the website is not any more existing, the corresponding variable should “a” (not “m”).

Table 4 provides some examples.

Table 4. Entity table

The English name has been added for readability, but it is not included in the table

Entity ID	English name	Entity foundation year	Entity foundation remark	Entity closure year	Entity closure remark	Website
FI0025	Aalto University	2011	Founded 2011 as an outcome of a merger	a		http://www.aalto.fi
FR0174	Université Paris 1 - Panthéon Sorbonne	1971	Split of the old Sorbonne university in the 12 universities of the Paris region	a		https://www.univ-paris1.fr/
IT0009	University of Bologna	1088	Original foundation	a		http://www.unibo.it
CH0017	UAS of Southern Switzerland	1997	Creation of University of Applied Sciences, with new statute and mandate, by merging already existing cantonal schools.	a		http://www.supsi.ch
BE0063	EHSAL University college Brussels	2007	merge between KUB, EHSAL, HONIM and VLEKHO	2013	merged with BE0079 into BE0090 on 1.1.2014	a
CY0020	Cyprus College of Art	1969		2011	stopped operation in academic year 2012/2013	a

7.2 Entity characteristics table

The register includes a minimum of variables with the goal of making the matching with other databases easier. All these variables are recorded for a specific period of time, so that change of name and location can be tracked even when they are not associated with a demographic event. Each set of characteristics is attributed a start year and an end year. When at least one characteristic is changed, a new record will be added to the corresponding table.

Set of characteristics should have consecutive years (one set ending in year Y, the following starting in the same year or at Y+1). The first set of characteristics should be set at the earlier year when the information is available. The last of characteristics will always have “a” as an end date, meaning that the characteristics were still valid in the last year of update of the register.

7.2.1 Legal name

The name of the entity as it is adopted by the entity itself (will correspond in many cases, but not all of them, with the legal name). Importantly, when an entity changes of names without a demographic event, the ID remains the same, but a new set of characteristics is entered in the register. This also includes name changes related to changes in status (Hogeschoole > University).

For the English name, the English official translation should be used. When it does not exist, semi-official translations are allowed (like the name adopted on Wikipedia).

7.2.2 Acronym

The official and most widely used acronym (for example CNRS, MPG, etc.). It is included to make name matching easier.

7.2.3 Country of establishment

The country of establishment refers to the country where the entity receives its own legal identity, referring for example to the legal status (country of registration) or the country which provides the public mission of the entity. In most cases, this will be identical to the country of the legal seat with following exceptions:

- Components of foreign entities will have the country of the establishment of the parent (Max Planck Institute in Netherlands is established in Germany). Affiliated units which are independent on their own will have the country of their own seat.
- International organizations based on intergovernmental treaties and agreements, such as the OECD, will receive the code “INT” independently of their legal seat.
- Entities which are part of the European Commission structure (executive agencies, Joint Research Centre) will receive the code “INT” independently of their legal seat.

7.2.4 Entity level

This variable distinguishes whether the entity is a group, an organization or a component of an organization. Codes as in Table 5 apply.

Table 5. Entity level codes

Level	Code
Group of organizations	1
Organization	2
Component	3
Consortium	4

7.2.5 Type of entity

The type of entity is introduced in the register in order to allow user limiting the extraction only to a subset of the considered organizations.

Entities can be attributed multiple types (for example PRO and research funding organization) and have to be separated with “,”. Further, types are attributed for specific time period, so that it is possible that organizations change of type across time by keeping their identity.

Example: a PRO might fulfil also the function of research funding organization for a period of time, but stops this function (for example by governmental decision) at some time, without this changing its identity. The PRO will thus keep its ID, but has two distinct records specifying its functions (PRO and research funding organization, respectively only research funding organization).

For definition of types refer to section 3 of this handbook.

Table 6. Codes for types of entities.

Type	Code
Higher Education Institutions	1
Public Research Organizations	2
Research funding organizations	3
Research Hospital	4
Public administration organization	5
Private non profit	6
Charities	7
Research Technology Organizations	8
Other	9

7.2.6 Variables

- Entity ID. A *unique* identifier for the entity.
- Characteristics ID (a unique identifier for the characteristics in certain periods). This ID is constructed as an extension of the entity ID as follows: "CHAR" + Entity ID + "-X". Since entities can have more than one set of characteristics, IDs are distinguished by -1, -2 etc. (e.g. CHARAT0001-1, CHARAT0001-2).
- Legal name of the entity in national language. Text.
- Legal name of the entity in English. Text.
- Acronym. Text.
- Characteristics start year. Numeric, 4 digits.
- Remarks on characteristics start year. Text.
- Characteristics end year. Numeric, 4 digits.
- Remarks on characteristics end year. Text.
- The country of establishment. Text (ISO code).
- Level of entity. Nominal.
- Type of entity. Nominal.

Remarks:

- Organizations will have at least a set of characteristics with end year "a" (the currently valid one) except when they have been closed in the meantime. In the latter case, the last set of characteristics should have the closure year as end year. Code "m" is not allowed for the characteristics end year.
- When there is no information on when a set of characteristics started (for example when the organization received its current name) code "m" should be used for the start year. This is interpreted in any case as meaning that the set of characteristics is valid already in the year 2000.
- When there are more sets of characteristics the later set receive as start year either the same year of the end of the previous set or same year plus one (2005 and 2005 or 2005 and 2006).
- For entities with foundation year after 2000, the first set of characteristics should receive start year = foundation year, as characteristics changes are recorded from that date.

Table 7 provides some examples of the entity characteristics table displaying some cases which might occur. University of Bologna has a unique set of characteristics for the whole period from

the foundation year, whereas CH0016 changed its name in 2007 and hence it is recorded with two (consecutive) set of characteristics. The latter example shows the flexibility of keep distinct the list of IDs and the related organizational characteristics.

Table 7. Excerpt of the entity characteristics table

ID	Entity_ID	Legal name	English name	Country	Entity_level	Entity_type	Start year	Start year remarks	End year	End year remarks
1	IT0009	Università di Bologna	University of Bologna	IT	1	1	1088	foundation	a	
2	CH0016	Fachhochschule Zentralschweiz	Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts	CH	1	1	1997	foundation	2007	name changed to Hochschule Luzern in autumn 2007
3	CH0016	Hochschule Luzern	University of Applied Sciences of Lucerne	CH	1	1	2007	name changed to Hochschule Luzern in autumn 2007	a	

7.3 Demographic events table

For sake of simplicity, demographic events are coded for full years.

7.3.1 Variables

Demographic events are registered in a specific table including the following variables:

- Demographic event ID (a unique identifier for a demographic event). Text + Integer, “Demo” + country code + 3 digits, start with 001 for each entity + “1” to distinguish lines
- Parent ID. The unique entity IDs of the organization which existed before the event. Text.
- Child ID. The unique entity IDs of the organization which existed after the event. Text.
- Year of demographic event. The last year when the parent organization(s) existed. Numeric, 4 digits. Code “m” is not allowed.
- Type of demographic event. Nominal.
- Remarks on demographic event, which include a short description of the event. Text.

Demographic event IDs are stable and should not be reassigned.

This table will record demographic events from the year 2000 onwards. Previous events might be recorded in the entity table under the remarks field for the foundation year.

Special organizational IDs are included to track cases where no IDs could be inserted in order to avoid blank cells in the tables:

- ID ZZ0001 when the organization is not included in the register and therefore an ID cannot be attributed (e.g. a merger of two organizations not in the register).

All demographic events are binary, i.e. involve only one parent and child entity. Events which involve multiple parent or multiple child entities, namely mergers and split, are treated through multiple lines in the demographic event table, which *carry the same demographic event code* (see Table 8 for an overview).

Therefore a single event might correspond to more than one line in the database with the same event ID. Combinations event ID*parent ID*child ID are however unique by construction.

Table 8. Standard codes for demographic events and rules for handling IDs.

Event	Code	Parent IDs	Child IDs
Merger	5	Multiple lines each with one parent ID.	Single
Split	6	Single	Multiple lines with one child ID.
Take-over	7	Single, the ID of the taken-over entity	Single (the taking-over entity)
Spin-out	8	Single (the original entity)	Single, ID of the spin-out- entity.

Demographic events will be documented from the year 2000 onwards, previous events are not recorded and may be mentioned in the entity table under remarks.

The table below provides an excerpt to the events table of register displaying these choices.

Table 9. Examples of demographic events

Demographic event ID	Parent ID	Child ID	Year of demographic event	Type of demograph	Remarks on demographic event
Demo_ID	Demo_parent_ID	Demo_child_ID	Demo_year	Demo_type	Demo_remarks
Text+integer ("Demo"+country code+3 digits, start with 001 for each entity)	Entity ID(s), code ZZ0001 if organization is not included in the register	Entity ID(s), code ZZ0001 if organization is not included in the register	Year	nominal (merger=5, split=6, take-over=7, spin-out=8)	Text
DEMOCH001	CH0025	CH0017	2009	7	Take-over
DEMOCH002	CH0027	CH0036	2011	6	Split into three cantonal schools
DEMOCH002	CH0027	CH0037	2011	6	Split into three cantonal schools
DEMOCH002	CH0027	CH0038	2011	6	Split into three cantonal schools
DEMOCH003	CH1011	CH0011	2008	7	Since 2008 ISREC was integrated in
DEMOCH004	CH0801	CH0013	2003	7	Integration

7.4 Linkages between entities

This table records linkages between entities in the register. Following general rules apply:

- All linkages are binary, i.e. when there are multiple linkages (for example a group composed by four organizations), different lines should be entered. This enables recording changes in groups.
- All linkages are time-stamped, meaning that they have a start and end date.

7.4.1 Variables

The linkages table includes following variables.

- Linkage ID: a unique identifier for linkages. Text + Integer, "Link" + country code + 3 digits, start with 001 for each entity.
- Linked Entity ID1. The ID of the first linked entity.
 - In case of a membership, this variable includes the higher ranked entity (see example below).
- Linked Entity ID2. The ID of the first linked entity.
 - In case of a membership, this variable includes the lower ranked entity (see example below).
- Linkage start year. The first year for which the linkage is valid. Numeric, 4 digits.
 - Code "m" should be used when there is no information.
- Linkage end year. The last year for which the linkage is valid. Numeric, 4 digits.
 - Code "a" should be used for still existing links at the last update of the register. Code "m" is not allowed for the linkage end year.
- Linkage type. A variable characterizing the type of linkage (see Table 10).

- Linkage remarks. A remark field characterizing the linkage. Text.

Table 10. Standard codes for linkage types and related consistency rules

Event	Code	Entity 1	Entity 2	Remarks
Membership	1	Component Organization Organization	Organization Group Consortium	One linkage for each member entity
Affiliated	2	Organization	Organization	One line for each affiliation relationships
Association	3	Organization	Organization	
Joint unit	4	Organization	Organization	Recorded once even if there are multiple such units. Details might be added in the remarks to the linkage.

Remark: when the start year of the linkage is not known, code “m” should be used.

Linkages IDs are stable and should not be reassigned.

Table 11. Excerpt of the linkages table

Linkage ID	Linked entity ID1	Linked entity ID2	Linkage start year	Linkage end year	Linkage type	Remarks on linkages
Link_ID	Link_entity_ID1	Link_entity_ID2	Link_start_year	Link_end_year	Link_type	Link_remarks
Text+integer ("Link"+country code+3 digits, start with 001 for each entity)	Entity ID, code ZZ0001 if organization is not included in the register	Entity ID, code ZZ0001 if organization is not included in the register	Year (m=information missing)	Year (a=not applicable)	nominal membership=1, affiliated=2, association=3, joint unit=4)	Text
LINKCH001	CH1012	CH0010	2010	a		2 Affiliation since 2010
LINKCH002	CH0011	CH1009	2008	a		3 Association since 2008
LINKCH004	CH2001	CH0001	1999	a		3
LINKCH005	CH2002	CH0001	m	a		2 Shared locations, intergation of staff.
LINKCH006	CH2003	CH0002	m	a		2 Shared locations
LINKCH007	CH2004	CH0004	1995	a		2 Shared locations
LINKCH008	CH2005	CH0005	1890	a		2 Shared locations
LINKCH009	CH2006	CH0009	1945	a		3
LINKCH010	CH2007	CH0009	m	a		3
LINKCH011	CH2008	CH0009	m	a		2 Shared locations, integration of staff

7.4.2 The joint unit linkages

Joint unit linkages conform the general rules as follows:

- The joint unit’s linkages connects two entities at the same level (organization – organization) and is binary. If a unit is joint between three organizations, three separate lines should be included as in the example below.
- In most cases, the joint units will not be entered in the register as a separate entity, but indicated in the remarks section of the link.
- When the joint units is in the register as a component, the membership linkages with the parent organizations will be entered separately from the joint unit linkages (which will not be affected), as in the example below.
- In principle, it is possible that two organizations have more than one joint unit linkages, but this case should considered exceptional and restricted to cases where the joint units are very distinct (for example located on two different places).

Table 12. Coding of joint units linkages

Linkage ID	Linked entity ID1	Linked entity ID2	Linkage start year	Linkage end year	Linkage type	Remarks on linkages
Link_ID	Link_entity_ID1	Link_entity_ID2	Link_start_year	Link_end_year	Link_type	Link_remarks
Text+integer ("Link"+country code+3 digits, start with 001 for each entity)	Entity ID, code ZZ0001 if organization is not included in the register	Entity ID, code ZZ0001 if organization is not included in the register	Year (m=information missing)	Year (a=not applicable)	nominal membership=1, affiliated=2, association=3, joint unit=4)	Text
LINKAT007	AT1022	AT0008	1994	2002		1 joint unit of 3 universities
LINKAT008	AT1022	AT0005	1994	2002		1 joint unit of 3 universities
LINKAT009	AT1022	AT0009	1994	2002		1 joint unit of 3 universities
LINKAT012	AT0008	AT0005	1994	2002		4 joint unit AT1022
LINKAT013	AT0008	AT0009	1994	2002		4 joint unit AT1022
LINKAT014	AT0005	AT0009	1994	2002		4 joint unit AT1022

7.5 Location of the local establishments

This table will include the coordinates of all local establishments of an entity, as they can be identified by clustering the addresses linked to that establishment in the IFRIS-PATSTAT and in the Leiden ranking databases. This information is relevant to connect OrgReg with spatial and regional analysis.

Additionally, information on the legal seat is integrated in this table from descriptive evidence, like the organizational website and Internet sources.

Information in this table will be limited to the geographical coordinates of local establishments and to their period of validity. No identification or characterization of the local establishments is foreseen, but the legal seat of the organization is singled out as it might be used as a reference location for most purposes.

7.5.1 Variables

Therefore the table will include following variables:

- Entity ID. The entity ID associated to that location. Text, 6 digits as above.
- Location ID. A unique identifier for each location. Text + integer. This ID is constructed as an extension of the entity ID as follows: "LOCAT" + entity_ID.
 - Since entities can have more than one location, IDs are distinguished by -1, -2 etc. (for example LOCATAT0001-1, LOCATAT0001-2, etc.).
- Location start year. The first year when the location is valid. Numeric, 4 digits.
 - Use "m" if exact start date is not known. This is interpreted in any case as meaning that the location existed already in the year 2000.
- Location end year. The last year when the location is valid. Numeric, 4 digits.
 - Use "a" if location is still valid.
- Geographical coordinates. Longitude and latitude of the location. Numeric.
- Legal seat. This variable identifies whether the location corresponds to the legal seat as it can be identified from the organization documents. Nominal.
- Country of location. Text, ISO code.
- City of the location. Text.
- Postcode. Text.
- NUTS region of the location at level NUTS 3 (NUTS-2016 edition; <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/overview>). For countries not using NUTS, like Israel, OECD level-3 codes are used (TL3).
- Location remarks. Text.

7.5.2 Remarks and special codes:

- When a location is still valid at the last update of the register, location end date should be set to “a”.
- In the same year, only one legal seat location is allowed.

Table 13 lists demographic events and their implications in terms of organizational identifiers.

Table 13. Demographic events and how they are handled in OrgReg

Demographic Event		Change of identifier (ID)	Handling in OrgReg
Foundation. The creation of a new entity. (Defining the name, place).	Closure: The complete closure of activities of an existing entity.	New independent identifier (ID) introduced in the case of births. Identifiers of disappearing organizations are reserved and not reused.	Foundation and closure are directly handled in the corresponding entity table by the foundation and closure year. They are not recorded separately as events.
Merger between two entities in a new entity (death of the merged entities, new name, legal status, accreditation etc.). The (date of the) merger corresponds to the (year of) birth (foundation) or entry.	Split of an existing entity into two or more independent entities (two or more new entities, new name, accreditation, maybe legal status).	New independent identifier (ID) introduced analogously to births. Identifiers of antecedent organizations are reserved and not reused. Metadata of the register allow the connection of interlinked IDs.	Mergers and splits are recorded separately as demographic events, while individual entities involved receive also the corresponding foundation and closure year.
Take-over of one entity by another one (death of the entity which was taken over, the taking over entity continues to exist). The new entity retains the identity of the entity taking over, if name and location are not changed.	Spin-out. Split-off of a section of an entity to become a separate institute (old entity exists unchanged, new entity has new name, legal status, accreditation, governance, etc.). The remaining unit keeps name, legal status and location of the previous entity.	In the case of take-overs, the identifier of the dominant organization taking over another will be held (even if this organization is smaller than the organization taken over). The identity of the organization taken over is reserved and not reused. In the case of spin-outs, the ID of the original organization will continue. Analogously to a birth, a new ID is created for the new organization spinning out. Metadata of the register allow the connection of interlinked IDs.	Take-overs and spin-outs are handled separately as a demographic events. The entity taken-over receives the corresponding closure year, while the spin-out receives the corresponding closure year.

Demographic events are registered in a specific table of the register (see section 7.3), with the exception of birth and closure which are recorded directly in the entity table as they are unique to each entity.

7.6 Indicators table

This table stores research output indicators as described in section 6. Since indicators come either directly from Knowmak or from other sources, two different ways of storing data can be used:

- Use a mixed approach: load indicators coming from Knowmak via API and store other indicators in the OrgReg database.

- Retrieve Knowmak data once a month and store all indicators in the OrgReg database (acceptable, since data are not updated very frequently)

The final way of data storage will be defined after discussing it in detail with the technical team.

7.6.1 Data structure

Indicators are stored in a separate table in the OrgReg database including the following fields:

- OrgReg ID: the identifier of the concerned entity.
- Reference year: the reference year to which the indicator refer.
- Indicator country: country code of entity
- Indicator region: the NUTS code of the region; this field is 'aggregated' for aggregated data at the organizational level.
- OrgReg_P: number of publications for the entity, reference year and region.
- OrgReg_Ptop10%: number of publications in the top10% cited for the entity, reference year and region.
- OrgReg_Pint: number of publications with international collaboration for the entity, reference year and region.
- OrgReg_Pat: number of priority patents for the entity, reference year and region.
- OrgReg_Pattrans: number of transnational priority patents for the entity, reference year and region.
- OrgReg_EUpart: number of participations in EU-FP projects cited for the entity, reference year and region.
- OrgReg_EUcoord: number of coordinations of EU-FP projects cited for the entity, reference year and region.
- Linked entities IDs: identifiers of linked entities (relevant to analyse whether this might affect indicators).
- Demographic events IDs: identifiers of demographic events affecting entities (relevant to analyse whether this might affect indicators).

As in the panel data menu, tables for demographic events and linkages will be added in order to show all corresponding events for selected entities.

8 Technical implementation of OrgReg

The structure of the OrgReg has been designed in order to store information in a consistent and flexible way. It consists of two parts:

- The register, including a database and user interface with possibilities for searching and exporting register data and additional indicators.
- An organizational subregister (RISIS-ETER) for higher education data, which in the first step includes the European Tertiary Education Register plus additional RISIS data like publications and participations to EU-FP.

8.1.1 Technical implementation of the register

The choice of technology for the implementation of the register is dedicated to deal with its current structure and allows flexibility for further extensions in the application and data structure. Thus, the application will be written using the modern MEAN (MongoDB, ExpressJS, AngularJS, NodeJS) stack. The free and open source JavaScript software stack ensures that one language can be used for both the server-side and client-side environments.

- MongoDB

MongoDB is a NoSQL (Not only SQL) database, which means that there are no tables in the database, but collections. These collections can be viewed as tables with the additional possibility to structure data within a collection.

Because of the intended usage of the database, an object oriented database will be chosen over a relational one. An object oriented database allows a higher degree of flexibility for the OrgReg, since it is way more complex to split the data into tables than to use collections instead. Also, object oriented databases are usually faster than relational ones when there are many joins (used to combine rows from two or more tables, based on a common field between them) involved. MongoDB allows you to store your data flexibly, which means that you do not have to know everything you want to store by name and type, like you would in a relational database. This is a major time-saver when handling lots of different types and with lots of different sources of data. It can also mean that your application may grow dynamically without any or only moderate changes in program code. The following example shows how data would be stored in a relational and an object oriented database.

Table 14: Differences between a relational and object oriented database

Relational database	MongoDB
Table	Collection
Row	Document
Index	Index
JOIN	Embedded Document or Reference

Figure 5: Relational and object oriented data storage and query

Source: <http://crocodillon.com/blog/mongodb-for-dbas-introduction>.

- ExpressJS

ExpressJS is a web application server framework, which is used in order to build web applications. It is the backend part of the MEAN stack and the standard server framework for NodeJS.

- AngularJS

Besides the MongoDB database, the user interface will be the heart of the OrgReg application. The UI (user interface) will be created using the AngularJS framework, which is a JavaScript web framework for creating single page web applications. The interface between front-end and the server consists of a set of calls following the REST Interface specification. These API calls are used by the application front-end, but may also be called from other sources (if authenticated). All data operations possible in the OrgReg application will be accessible via an API call following the REST interface specification. This allows a clean and well documented separation of the visualization layer from the logic components on the server side, allowing the clients to evolve, without changing the server part. The API documentation is part of the application documentation and may also be used by third party applications, if authenticated. The connection of external tools is not in the scope of the initial implementation, but the API will be built with the possibility of extension.

AngularJS supports modern single page application concepts, such as the 2-way data binding (automatic synchronization of data between the model and view components), which makes the UI feel application-like (components resemble a desktop application) and allow a fluent workflow, since only data and not whole HTML-pages are sent to and from the server. It is planned to build the API with the swagger.io toolset (YAML-formatted interface description), that provides a good documentation and specification for the API. The swagger toolset also supports code generation for an interface, that makes it easy to provide access to the API for a long list of offered platforms and languages (like Scala, Go, Python, Objective-C, C#, Ruby and many more).

- NodeJS

NodeJS is used for developing server-side web applications. The benefits when using NodeJS for the server code is that it is fast and does not need a lot of resources to run. It, as well as in the front-end, uses Javascript as programming. This is comfortable for the developers and allows sharing code between front and backend, reducing redundancy. There are a lot of open source packages available as "node packages", making it possible to add features at low cost. The language is very alive at the moment, so there is a large

amount of developers and support available for NodeJS. It also integrates seamlessly with the other parts of the application, as they all speak some common language.

8.1.2 Access levels

The OrgReg application was extended by additional features in order to give the administrator and data deliverer more possibilities. For this aim, the new role of data manager was created for this group. The following roles have been defined in OrgReg:

- User: all users with a RISIS account have access to the OrgReg data and can export them.
- Data manager: OrgReg data deliverer have now the role of data manager. They can, additionally to users, also export data collection files from the interface and have access to the change logs in order to reproduce previous updates.
- Admin: additionally to users and data mangers, administrators can edit data and make changes in the data structure.

8.1.3 Authentication

The authentication mechanism uses the OAuth2 standard, which allows for a high flexibility for connecting external tools to the OrgReg API. Authentication of the register is connected with the RISIS access facility.

Users should, first, create a Cortext account at <https://risis.cortext.net> and accept the RISIS code and conduct for usage of data and then they are automatically authenticated to the OrgReg platform.

The entire authentication in Cortext is handled by the Cortext-Authentication module. This is also where the profile management sits. The other modules access it with its API, with a special access token. The Auth module is based on OAuth2 standard. The authentication and authorization workflow follow the OAuth2 three-legged standard. The authorization code grant type is used to obtain both access tokens and refresh tokens and is optimized for confidential clients. Since this is a redirection-based flow, the client must be capable of interacting with the resource owner's user-agent (typically a web browser) and capable of receiving incoming requests (via redirection) from the authorization server. See the figure below on the authorization code flow.

Figure 6: Authorization Code Flow

Source: CORTEXT – Auth Documentation

The code flow in the figure above includes the following steps:

- (A) The client initiates the flow by directing the resource owner's user-agent to the authorization endpoint. The client includes its client identifier, requested scope, local state, and a redirection URI to which the authorization server will send the user-agent back once access is granted (or denied).
- (B) The authorization server authenticates the resource owner (via the user-agent) and establishes whether the resource owner grants or denies the client's access request.
- (C) Assuming the resource owner grants access, the authorization server redirects the user-agent back to the client using the redirection URI provided earlier (in the request or during client registration). The redirection URI includes an authorization code and any local state provided by the client earlier.
- (D) The client requests an access token from the authorization server's token endpoint by including the authorization code received in the previous step. When making the request, the client authenticates with the authorization server. The client includes the redirection URI used to obtain the authorization code for verification.
- (E) The authorization server authenticates the client, validates the authorization code, and ensures that the redirection URI received matches the URI used to redirect the client in step (C). If valid, the authorization server responds back with an access token and, optionally, a refresh token.

8.1.4 User interface of the register

The design of the user interface is dedicated to the intended usages, as expressed through user scenarios. Its main parts will be functions to search, filter and export data from the register.

The following table gives an overview on some relevant user scenarios:

Table 15. List of user scenarios

Scenario	Content
Cross-sectional analysis	A list of all entities active in one given year including the descriptive information.
Spatial analysis	A list of all entities which belonged to a specific region, based on NUTS 3 regions.
Longitudinal analysis	A list of entities * year for a given period including some basic information.
Demographic events	A list of demographic events including the descriptive information, involved entities, etc. for certain years.
Linkages data	A list of all linkages including also the entity name..
Entity list	The list of entities active in a given period.

The heterogeneous structure of the different tables in the register requires a division into two ways of extracting data from the register. The first option enables the user to explore active institutions in a certain time period including some characteristics. The second option allows the user to retrieve panel data from the register. Both options are described in more detail in the following sections:

1) Search for active entities and corresponding information

This option enables the user to retrieve a list of active entities in certain years or periods and explore the full dataset of the register regarding these entities. The search function includes the following variables:

- Year: the user can choose one or several years between 2000 and the most current year using a slider. When a foundation year in the data is missing ('m'), it is assumed that the entity is active since at least the year 2000.
- Country of location: users can select their country of interest, multi-selection is possible.
- Level of entity: the user can choose the level of entity, multi-selection is possible.
- Type of entity: similar to the option above, users can choose the type of entity, where multi-selection is also possible.
- Text search: enables users to search for specific terms like institution names, acronyms, cities etc.
- Timestamp search: user can search for entities, which were created or modified (the data) from a specific date.

Using the selection options from above allows the user to extract all information for the entities of interest. This means that the result of the search will include all data rows in all of the five tables, where a detected entity appears. The result will be displayed in table grids (one tab for each table), where users can further filter in their search results. The tables can then be exported separately in order to exploit the register data. The exported tables will have the structure showed in Table 16. Possible usages of this option are:

- A list of active entities in a certain period.
- A list of characteristics of these entities during the considered period (multiple characteristics possible).

- A list of linkages of active institutions in a certain period, including also the current names of the entities.
- A list of demographic events of active institutions and involved entities, including also the current names of the entities.
- A list of locations of these entities during the considered period (multiple periods possible).

2) Retrieve panel data from the register

In order to display the register data in a multi-annual format, users can choose option 'Panel data'. This option includes the same variables in the search function as option with the big difference that only the main seat of an entity will be displayed. This is necessary in order to receive a data structure, which enables the observation of register data over time.

The panel data option will include three tables:

- Entity*year table which also includes the characteristics and location of legal seat for that year (one row per entity*year).
- A list of linkages of active entities in a certain period, including also the current names of the entities.
- A list of demographic events of active entities, including also the current name of the entities.

If there was a change in characteristics or linkages within a selected year (end year of former characteristic = start year of the new characteristic and thus two rows instead of one), the observation where searched year is equal to the end year will be assigned. The panel data will be especially helpful when doing cross-sectional or longitudinal analysis using the register data. The result of the panel data search will be a table, where the user can choose the variables to be exported. It will be possible to export the full spreadsheet for the three tables as well as single variables.

Table 16: Structure of export tables of list of active institution

Entity table:

Entity ID	Entity current name	Entity synonym	Entity foundation year	Remarks on foundation year	Entity closure year	Remarks on closure year	Website of entity	Wikipedia website
BAS.ENTITYID	BAS.ENTITYNAME	BAS.ENTITYSYNONYM	BAS.FOUNDEAR	BAS.NOTESFOUNDEAR	BAS.ENTITYCLOSUREYEAR	BAS.NOTESENTITYCLOSURE	BAS.WEBSITE	BAS.WIKIPEDIA

Characteristics table:

Entity ID	Characteristics ID	Name of entity	English name of entity	Acronym	Characteristics start year	Remarks on characteristics start year	Characteristics end year	Remarks on characteristics end year	Country of establishment	Level
BAS.ENTITYID	CHAR.CHARID	CHAR.INSTNAME	CHAR.INSTNAMEENGL	CHAR.ACRONYM	CHAR.CHARSTARTYEAR	CHAR.NOTESCHARSTARTYEAR	CHAR.CHARENDEAR	CHAR.NOTESCHARENDEAR	CHAR.CHARCOUNTRYESTABL	CHAR.CHARLEVEL

Demographics table:

Demographic event ID	Parent ID	English name of parent entity	Child ID	English name of child entity	Year of demographic event	Type of demographic event	Remarks on demographic event
DEMO.EVENTID	DEMO.PARENTID	DEMO.PARENTNAMEENGL	DEMO.CHILDID	DEMO.CHILDNAMEENGL	DEMO.EVENTYEAR	DEMO.EVENTTYPE	DEMO.NOTES

Linkages table:

Linkage ID	Linked entity ID1	English name of linked entity 1	Linked entity ID2	English name of linked entity 2	Linkage start year	Linkage end year	Linkage type	Remarks on linkages
LINK.ID	LINK.ENTITY1ID	LINK.ENTITY1NAMEENGL	LINK.ENTITY2ID	LINK.ENTITY2NAMEENGL	LINK.STARTYEAR	LINK.ENDYEAR	LINK.TYPE	LINK.NOTES

Location table:

Location_ID	Location name English	Location start year	Location end year	Geographical coordinates - latitude	Geographical coordinates - longitude	Legal seat	Country of location	City of the location	Postcode	NUTS 3 region	Location remarks
LOCAT.LOCATID	LOCAT.INSTNAMEENGL	LOCAT.STARTYEAR	LOCAT.ENDYEAR	LOCAT.COORDLAT	LOCAT.COORDLONG	LOCAT.LEGALSEAT	LOCAT.LOCATCOUNTRY	LOCAT.CITY	LOCAT.POSTCODE	LOCAT.NUTS3	LOCAT.NOTESREMARKS

Compared to the last version of the OrgReg register, users have the possibility to look at entity details. This means that users can click on entity IDs and a separate window with all relevant information for this institution will emerge. It will also be possible to further examine linked entities within the entity details window. Additionally, users have the possibility to extract the register data via API. A detailed API documentation is available on the OrgReg web application.

8.1.5 User interface for the indicators

Data are made available to users in a separate indicator tab in the OrgReg user interface. The tab has a similar structure as the panel data tab. However it might include additional years since entities might have indicators also for year for which it did not exist.

The indicators module will include a new search function, since the search options will differ from the choices user have in the register module. The search function will at the beginning include a search for year ranges, countries/regions and a text search. As the project evolves, a search for topics may be added.

Indicators can be selected under the ‘variables’ tab alongside other relevant variables. OrgReg characteristics variables are left empty for the years for which the entity did not exist. Besides indicators, users can select variables from 3 register tables: entities, characteristics and locations.

Additionally, the indicators tab includes a selection option for the level of aggregation:

- Aggregated: only totals by entity*year are shown.
- Regional breakdown: numbers by entity*year*region are shown.

Data from Knowmak will be extracted directly from the Knowmak database via API. Additional data need to be imported into the OrgReg database from the administrator. For this aim, the admin section will be extended by a flexible import function, which allows the administrator to import data by Entity ID*year. In order to reproduce changes, the administrator will also have access to the change logs in a separate table grid.

8.1.6 Data validation and quality within the register

In order to ensure a high data quality level within the register, a standardized and reproducible process has been implemented where three different types of checks will be performed:

Table 17: Types of checks performed before the final quality analysis

Type of checks	Description	Procedure
Accuracy checks	Accuracy checks verify that data entered have the right format foreseen by the handbook and that no logically impossible values are found.	Accuracy checks are performed in the data collection. Simple mistakes are corrected directly, whereas unclear cases are reported back for clarification.
Completeness checks	No blank cells are allowed in the dataset, except for remarks. Blanks should be recoded correctly as missing, confidential, not applicable or "0". This control is extremely important for the final quality of the database.	Blank cells are highlighted automatically. Clear cases are recoded directly and ambiguous cases (for example between missing and not applicable) are reported back for clarification.

Consistency checks	These checks control for logical consistency between different variables (for example a start year cannot be later an end year). Rules in this respect are stipulated in the handbook.	Deviant values are identified and checked. In case there are specific reasons, an explanation is added for that specific institution.
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Since the data for the register are added via Microsoft Excel templates, a first wave of checks (using conditional formatting and colouring of inconsistencies) is already implemented within the templates. This allows the data deliverer as well as the data collector to recognize any inconsistencies immediately and correct or explain them. Since MS-Excel files are also vulnerable, there will be a final phase of checks when the data are imported into the database. A full list of checks can be found in the following tables, where Table 18 shows all checks implemented in MS-Excel and the import and

Table 19 shows additional checks implemented in check scripts, which run during the data import.

Table 18: Full list of variables and accuracy, completeness and consistency checks included also in the MS-Excel template

Variable	Check
Entity ID	alarm if cell is not empty but value has not 6 characters
Entity current name (English)	alarm if cell is empty
Entity foundation year	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not 4 characters and is not "m" OR if value is a year and value in "Entity closure year" is also a year and value in this cell is larger than value in "Entity closure year"
Remarks on foundation year	
Entity closure year	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not 4 characters and is not "a" OR if value is a year and value in "Entity foundation year" is also a year and value in this cell is smaller than value in "Entity foundation year"
Remarks on closure year	
Website of entity	check for missing variables
Characteristics ID	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not between 12-13 characters
Name of entity	alarm if cell is empty
English name of entity	
Acronym	alarm if cell is empty
Characteristics start year	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not 4 characters and is not "m" OR if value is a year and value in "Characteristics end year" is also a year and value in this cell is larger than value in "Characteristics end year"
Remarks on characteristics start year	
Characteristics end year	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not 4 characters and is not "a" OR if value is a year and value in "Characteristics start year" is also a year and value in this cell is smaller than value in "Characteristics start year"
Remarks on characteristics start year	
Country of establishment	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not 2 characters and is not "m" or "INT"
Level of entity	alarm if cell is empty OR value is not 1, 2, 3, or "m"
Type of entity	alarm if cell is empty OR if value(s) do not include 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 or "m"
Demographic event ID	alarm if cell is not empty but has not 9 characters
Parent ID	alarm if cell is empty OR if number of characters is not 6
Child ID	alarm if cell is empty OR if number of characters is not 6
Year of demographic event	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not 4 characters
Type of demographic event	alarm if cell is empty OR if value is not 5, 6, 7 or 8 OR if value is 5 and "Year of demographic event" of "Child ID" is not "Entity foundation year" of child's "Entity ID"
Remarks on demographic event	
Linkage ID	alarm if cell is not empty but has not 9 characters
Linked entity ID1	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not 6 characters

Linked entity ID2	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not 6 characters
Linkage start year	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not 4 characters and is not "m" OR if value is a year and value in "Linkage end year" is also a year and value in this cell is larger than value in "Linkage end year"
Linkage end year	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not 4 characters and is not "a" OR if value is a year and value in "Linkage start year" is also a year and value in this cell is smaller than value in "Linkage start year"
Linkage type	alarm if cell is empty OR value is not 1, 2, 3 or 4 OR if linkage type is 1 and level of linked entity 1 is not larger than level of linked entity 2 OR if linkage type is 2, 3 or 4 and level of linked entity 1 is not equal to the level of linked entity 2
Remark on linkages	
Location_ID	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not between 13-14 characters
Location start year	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not 4 characters and is not "m" OR if value is a year and value in "Location end year" is also a year and value in this cell is larger than value in "Location end year"
Location end year	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not 4 characters and is not "a" OR if value is a year and value in "Location start year" is also a year and value in this cell is smaller than value in "Location start year"
Geographical coordinates - longitude	alarm if cell is empty
Geographical coordinates - latitude	alarm if cell is empty
Legal seat	alarm if cell is empty OR value is not 0, 1, or "m"
Country of location	alarm if cell is empty OR value has not 2 characters and is not "m"
City of the location	alarm if cell is empty
Postcode	alarm if cell is empty
NUTS 3 region	Alarm if cell is empty OR value has not 5 characters and is not "a" and is not "m"
Location remarks	

Table 19: Additional checks implemented within data import

Description
All active entities must have one characteristics and at least one location with end year "a" (the currently valid ones).
When there are more than one characteristic set for the same entity ID, the end year of the first must be the same (or year+1) as the start year of the second one
Consistency between demographic events and entities closure year: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parent IDs for mergers and taken-over entities should have the same closure year as the year of the demographic event. • The opposite for the child IDs: foundation year of the child of a merger and a spin-out should be the same as the year of the demographic event.
When an institution is closed (closure year) then there must be also a characteristics end year and a location end year for the same entity.
If type of entity is 1 and third character of Entity ID is not 0 OR if type of entity is 2 and third character of Entity ID is not 1 OR if type of entity is 4 and third character of Entity ID is not 2 OR if type of entity is 5 and third character of Entity ID is not 3 OR if type of entity is 6 and third character of Entity ID is not 4.
The current name must be identical to name in English entered into the entity-characteristics table for the currently valid set of characteristics (i.e. the characteristics with no end date, end date variable equal to "a").
Check for duplicate Entity IDs.
Mergers with the same ID for the child and the same year should have the same ID.
Splits with the same ID for the parent and the same year should have the same ID.
Entity IDs in characteristic, demographic, linkages and location must be also in the entity table.
Check for duplicate names and websites
All ETER IDs need to be included also in OrgReg

8.2 Technical implementation of the higher education subregister

The core part of the higher education subregister is represented by the European Tertiary Education Register, which will be extended by additional data included in RISIS. Thus, the subregister will base on the ETER architecture, which also uses an object-oriented approach and will be implemented using MongoDB. Different structured collections lead to a dynamic schema of the database itself, which leads to an iterative and agile approach for the design and development of the subregister. This implies that the structure of the database will change slightly by every added or withdrawn field (bits and pieces of data). Thus, if new fields need to be added to a collection, the field can be created without affecting all other collections in the system, without updating a central system catalogue and without taking the system offline. Also, if developers add more features, MongoDB continues to store the updated objects without the need for performing costly alteration operations, or worse - having to re design the schema from scratch.

The subregister database consists of some master data and the dynamic data collected via MS-Excel files. Important parts of the master data are the field collections. A field collection is a meta-description of a column within the HEI data collection MS-Excel files. The field description defines:

- The type of data that is stored in this field.
- The display labels for the represented column.
- The possible flags available for this field.
- A list of display and export formats.
- The link of the MS-Excel-Column ID and the data path within the database object.

The dynamic data are split into subdocuments in order to improve performance and data handling. Each HEI base document is linked to its subdocuments via a 1:1 connection. While the ETER data will be synchronized with the original ETER database and thus be up to date at any time, any changes in the additional RISIS datasets have also to be updated in the subregister by importing them again via API calls or MS-Excel files.

8.2.1 User interface of the subregister

The user interface of the subregister will be dedicated to the extraction and user friendly adaptation of higher education data by scholars of the regarding field. This includes the following:

- **Choose your HEI data**

In a first step, you can select year(s) and country(ies) of interest, before selecting the desired variables. During ETER, it proved useful to have the possibility of choosing groups of variables or single variables instead of having the whole spreadsheet at once. Thus, this feature will be implemented also in the user interface for the subregister. Additionally, filter can be applied in order to refine the selections.

- **Display and export settings**

Usability has a high priority for data analysts, which is taken into account by different display and export settings:

- o Choose either to see variable codes, special codes and flags or their labels.
- o Choose between two options of headers for variables:
 - Variable name, which includes a systematic variable naming, or
 - Variable label, which shows the full name of a column.
- o Choose between different export formats:
 - .csv (, or ; separated),
 - .xlsx (Microsoft Excel)
 - Machine ready datasets, which already include replacements for special codes (used to get more detail on missing data) usable in SPSS and STATA.

- **Export data**

Data can be exported in three different ways:

- Export all data, which means that you don't have to select variables, if you want to extract the whole dataset at once.
- Export visible data, which means that you can export exactly the data you have chosen by selections and filters.
- Export metadata, where you can retrieve the metadata corresponding to the chosen data.

8.3 Consistency between OrgReg register, RISIS-ETER and ETER

This section describes the procedures for synchronizing ETER, the OrgReg RISIS-ETER and the OrgReg Register, in order to avoid that there are inconsistencies between the same variables.

It covers three datasets:

- The register of public-sector organizations (OrgReg register), which provides a list of all public-sector organizations in Europe including some basic identification variables and tracking of demographic events.
- The European Tertiary Education Register database (ETER), which is the public official version of ETER managed by the ETER consortium.
- OrgReg RISIS-ETER, which is a version of ETER including some additional variables and years derived from other sources. This version is identical to the ETER official version for all the data included in the latter. Additional data either cover additional years or are new variables not included in ETER or new countries not included in ETER. Therefore, in RISIS-ETER the original data can be clearly distinguished from the data copied from ETER.

Data in the three databases can be edited from different sources:

- Through national statistical authorities (NSAs) or national experts (NEs) within the ETER project.
- Through the RISIS WP 6 project team, which is continuously working on the data. Data typically will be revised after web research or are already validated data from RISIS project partners (e.g. CWTS, AIT, IFRIS).
- Through other external sources, e.g. higher education institutions, which found out that their names or other data have been wrong in one of the databases.

In the past, this led to several iterated data corrections, where e.g. names have been corrected several times (official names from NSAs were corrected with names on websites, before in the next ETER data collection they have been again changed back to the official name in national statistics). These problems only affect few variables (e.g. names, foundation years), for most variables the data are clear. In order to solve this problem, the register data are defined to be the master data. Any changes in the register need to have explanations in the remark columns.

8.3.1 Identifiers

Identifiers (IDs) are at the core of the register and therefore they must be maintained and synchronized carefully between databases. Since the correct matching of IDs is preliminary to all other variables matching, the consistency checks for IDs must be run first and, once IDs have been aligned, the variables checks can be performed as well.

The general principles are that:

- All ETER IDs must be included also in the Register and in the RISIS-ETER (while both the Register and RISIS-ETER might include additional HEIs, for example HEIs which closed before the start of ETER data collection or additional countries and years for which data are provided).
- All RISIS-ETER IDs must be included also in the Register (while the register might include additional HEIs, for example HEIs which closed before the start of ETER data collection). This is already ensured by construction, since RISIS-ETER is a clone of ETER.
- IDs must be unique across all datasets and time. This is guaranteed by checking IDs and the corresponding names of the higher education institutions and reporting all cases where the same ID*year is associated with a different name as potentially suspect.

Checks

Check whether ETER IDs are included in the register:

- Output: a list of IDs and HEI names ETER not included in the Register. Since RISIS-ETER is a clone of ETER, IDs in both databases are the same by construction.
- This check is essential in order to update the register regularly.

Update of the ETER perimeter

When the ETER perimeter is revised for yearly data collection, the register ID list has to be previously checked since it might be more up to date.

8.3.2 Consistency between ETER and the OrgReg Register

The overlap of variables in ETER and the Register has different levels:

- Direct overlap, where a variable in ETER is equal to a variable in the Register (see Table 20). This is the case only with the main seat of an entity in OrgReg.
- Indirect overlap, where a variable in OrgReg is not directly in ETER, but can (and should) be derived from the existing data and added to ETER (in different variables, see Table 21).

The following dependencies exist between the two databases:

Table 20: Direct dependencies between ETER and OrgReg Register (main seat)

Description	Variable ETER	Variable OrgReg
Name (national language) to be equal	BAS.INSTNAME	CHAR.INSTNAME
Name (national English) to be equal	BAS.INSTNAMEENGL	CHAR.INSTNAMEENGL
Acronym to be equal	BAS.ACRONYM	CHAR.ACRONYM
Foundation year to be equal	BAS.FOUNDEYEAR	BAS.FOUNDEYEAR
Remarks on foundation year to be equal	BAS.NOTESFOUNDEYEAR	BAS.NOTESFOUNDEYEAR
Website to be equal	BAS.WEBSITE	BAS.WEBSITE
Postcode to be equal (for entities where LOCAT.LEGALSEAT is equal to 1)	GEO.POSTCODE	LOCAT.POSTCODE
NUTS 2 region to be taken from NUTS 3 region (first four characters; for entities where LOCAT.LEGALSEAT is equal to 1)	GEO.NUTS2	LOCAT.NUTS3
NUTS 3 region to be equal (for entities where LOCAT.LEGALSEAT is equal to 1)	GEO.NUTS3	LOCAT.NUTS3
City to be equal (for entities where LOCAT.LEGALSEAT is equal to 1)	GEO.CITY	LOCAT.CITY
Coordinates (latitude) to be equal (for entities where LOCAT.LEGALSEAT is equal to 1)	GEO.COORDLAT	LOCAT.COORDLAT
Coordinates (longitude) to be equal (for entities where LOCAT.LEGALSEAT is equal to 1)	GEO.COORDLON	LOCAT.COORDLON
Notes on region of establishment to be equal (for entities where LOCAT.LEGALSEAT is equal to 1)	GEO.NOTESREG	LOCAT.NOTESREG

Table 21: Indirect dependencies between ETER and OrgReg Register

Description	Variable ETER	Variable OrgReg
Hospital dummy - if there is a linkage entity id 1 or 2 with country code + 2xxx and an entity included in ETER in the other (again LINK.ENTITY1ID or LINK.ENTITY2.ID), then add dummy variable "1" in ETER in the variable BAS.UNIHOSP; if there is no linkage of this type, the dummy is 0 in ETER; If there exist several hospitals for an entity, separate them by ";	BAS.UNIHOSP	LINK.ENTITY1ID, LINK.ENTITY2ID
if there is a linkage entity id 1 or 2 with country code + 2xxx (e.g. "AT2001") and an entity included in ETER in the other (again LINK.ENTITY1ID or LINK.ENTITY2.ID), then add this entity id (i.e. the one starting with country code + 2) to the corresponding ETER ID in ETER (can only be the case when BAS.UNIHOSP = "1"); If there exist several hospitals for an entity, separate them by ";	BAS.UNIHOSPID	LINK.ENTITY1ID or LINK.ENTITY2ID (the one who has structure country code + 2xxx)
As above with entity name instead of entity id; If not hospital is linked to an HEI, add "a"	BAS.UNIHOSPNAME	LINK.ENTITY1NAMEENGL or LINK.ENTITY2NAMEENGL

If there exist several active locat IDs for an entity, the multiannual dummy in ETER needs to be "1"; if there exists only one active location, the dummy needs to be "0" in ETER	GEO.MULTISITE	LOCAT.LOCATID
Multiannual data - NUTS 3 regions of other campuses (i.e. if Legal seat = 0 in the Register) should be added in variable GEO.NUTS3MULTISITE in ETER (in one cell separated by ","); if there is only one active locat ID, add "a"	GEO.NUTS3MULTISITE	LOCAT.NUTS3, LOCAT.LEGALSEAT
Multiannual data - coordinates (latitude) of other campuses (i.e. if Legal seat = 0 in the Register) should be added in variable GEO.COORDLAT in ETER (in one cell separated by ","); if there is only one active locat ID, add "a"	GEO.MULTISITELAT	LOCAT.COORDLAT, LOCAT.LEGALSEAT
Multiannual data - coordinates (longitude) of other campuses (i.e. if Legal seat = 0 in the Register) should be added in variable GEO.COORDLON in ETER (in one cell separated by ","); if there is only one active locat ID, add "a"	GEO.MULTISITELON	LOCAT.COORDLON, LOCAT.LEGALSEAT
Multiannual data - city of other campuses (i.e. if Legal seat = 0 in the Register) should be added in variable GEO.CITY in ETER (in one cell separated by ","); if there is only one active locat ID, add "a"	GEO.MULTISITECITY	LOCAT.CITY, LOCAT.LEGALSEAT
Multiannual data - postcode of other campuses (i.e. if Legal seat = 0 in the Register) should be added in variable GEO.POSTCODE in ETER (in one cell separated by ","); if there is only one active locat ID, add "a"	GEO.MULTISITEPOSTCODE	LOCAT.POSTCODE, LOCAT.LEGALSEAT

In order to ensure data consistency between ETER and the OrgReg register, the checking mechanisms include all cases above. The output of the checks can be exported as .csv-file with warnings or errors about possible problems in the data. For differences in the content, the register is defined as master for specific variables. This means that the values for these variables in the register (e.g. names, cities, etc.) are overruling the values in ETER. In this case, changes for specific values can only be done in the register, since changes in ETER would vanish. During the synchronization run each night, an output is generated in order to have control on significant changes as deletions.

As already stated above, any changes e.g. in names, which can come from different sources, should be tracked by using the change-fields in the register. For this purpose, a change field for each register table has been added in the OrgReg register.

Important note: all changes in ETER coming from removing rows or replacing IDs in OrgReg need to be done by hand. Therefore, the administrator will be notified via email during the synchronization run when such cases occur.

Whenever running a data consistency check between ETER and the Register, the Register server sends an REST API request to ETER to retrieve the necessary comparison data in JSON format. The check is done in country-batches (loop over countries), or, when called during a Register data import, just for the country that is currently imported. As this consistency check

uses the already implemented data-check framework, check scripts may be added and changed freely at any time. Every time a data-check is run, it generates log of "info", "warning" and "error" entries that is stored in the DB and may be reviewed at any time by a Register Admin. These logs are displayed in a grid component in the browser and may be exported as a CSV file. A consistency check is run at every Register import between the Register and ETER. In case of differences of direct independencies, the administrator will be notified in the import menu.

8.3.3 ETER - RISIS-ETER

The RISIS-ETER database is a mirror of ETER. This means that the core data of RISIS-ETER are coming from ETER and are not edited within RISIS-ETER. Additional data in RISIS-ETER (e.g. patents, publications) are imported manually. In order to take-over changes in ETER (coming from NSAs or from the register), a synchronization process (by ETER ID and year) is running each night between ETER and RISIS-ETER (after ETER is synchronized from the register). ETER IDs not yet included in RISIS-ETER are added during the synchronization process.

8.3.4 Register - RISIS-ETER

Further, a check must be implemented in order to ensure that all RISIS-ETER IDs are also in the OrgReg register. This is necessary e.g. for EUMIDA data and any additional countries which will be added to RISIS-ETER (but not to ETER) in the future. Any further checks between the register and RISIS-ETER are obsolete because of the synchronization between ETER and the register on the one hand and ETER and RISIS-ETER on the other hand.

8.3.5 Synchronization process

The following synchronization takes place:

- qa-app: the qa-app runs every night and sends an email to the administrator if an ETER ID is not included in the register.
- Register - ETER: this process runs every night as cron job in order to synchronize all direct and indirect dependencies between register and ETER. It is also triggered after an import.
- ETER - RISIS-ETER: this process is taken-over from the former register version and ensures that RISIS-ETER is a mirror of ETER. The cron job is scheduled after the synchronization of the register and ETER.

9 Interlinking and data maintenance

A register such as OrgReg requires continuous updating: on the one hand, information from different sources might suggest the inclusion of additional entities; on the other hand, updates are also required by changes in organizations, such as mergers, closures and the birth of new entities.

This chapter explains processes for updating, maintenance and how changes are tracked in the register. It deals with following topics:

- The interlinking of Orgreg with other data sources, particularly other RISIS datasets, since these are also a major source for updates.
- How changes are tracked in the register.
- How updating of the data is managed.

9.1 Interlinking with other RISIS facilities

The link between the register and the other RISIS facilities is achieved through the introduction of the register IDs in the standardized actors table in the corresponding facilities. This applies currently to following facilities:

- The CWTS Web of Science database (<https://rcf.risis2.eu/dataset/3/metadata>).
- The IFRIS PATSTAT patent database (<https://rcf.risis2.eu/dataset/5/metadata>).
- The EUPRO database of European programs and projects (<https://rcf.risis2.eu/dataset/5/metadata>).

OrgReg identifiers are also used in the KNOWMAK central database (www.knowmak.eu) in order to produce indicators at the organizational level. It is envisaged to extent OrgReg identifiers to additional datasets with RISIS in the future.

This matching allows standardization of public research organizations across datasets and producing consistent indicators; it should however be remarked that the delineation of the perimeter of entities might differ by dataset (for example for what concerns the inclusion of linked entities).

The matching process usually comprises two steps:

a) A large-scale matching using name matching techniques, using the entity name(s), website, country and location. This allows identifying potential matches that are then verified manually, particularly for potentially ambiguous cases.

b) A more fine-grained check in which all public research entities are extracted from the databases and the cases not already matched and exceeding the OrgReg thresholds are verified manually. This process might lead to different outcomes:

- Adding additional entities to Orgreg.
- Identifying entities already in Orgreg, which have not been matched. In that case, the Orgreg ID is simply added.
- Cases where some categorization was incorrect in the source dataset. This includes for example a) incorrectly categorized entities (for example companies categorized as public entities), b) duplicates, c) components of OrgReg entities. All these case require some revision in the source dataset.

A log file is created, which indicates the action required for each case identified. Changes are done within OrgReg, respectively within the source dataset.

The process is repeated yearly in order that the matching is maintained to the most recent status.

9.2 Other source of changes and updates

OrgReg maintenance relies also on other information:

- New waves of data collection of the European Tertiary Education register (www.eter-project.com) imply updates of information on HEIs (for example mergers), as well as inclusion of new entities (since all HEIs in ETER are included in Orgreg) and corrections to the data. This process is managed automatically within OrgReg (see section **Error! Reference source not found.**).
- Information might provided by external users and associated datasets, such as the European Quality Assurance Register (www.eqar.eu). Such information is checked by the OrgReg team and then manually entered into the register.
- Regular checks made by the OrgReg team. To this purpose, the weblinks of the entities in OrgReg are checked every year, since redirected or broken links are usually a sign of demographic events or changes of names. Cases are manually checked and changes made in the register.

9.3 Maintenance process

The maintenance process is collectively shared by different organizations within RISIS participating to the OrgReg process and, specifically, those involved in the interlinked datasets.

Role are distributed as follows:

1. The OrgReg coordinating team is located at the Università della Svizzera italiana (USI) in Lugano. USI is responsible for the overall coordination of the development of OrgReg and for the development of the methodology.
Therefore, the USI team is responsible for most updates of the OrgReg database and for dealing with new methodological issues, in order to take standardized decisions.
2. OrgReg data managers are at RISIS partners who manage interconnected datasets, specifically Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT) and CWTS, University of Leiden. Data managers update Orgreg information based on their data sources; they consult the coordinating team for any issues which require collective decisions.
3. The OrgReg technical team is hosted by Joanneum research in Graz. The technical team is responsible for the maintenance and technical development of the database, as well as for entering all changes in the main database.

In order to manage the process, a specific infrastructure has been designed that allows a) extracting data collection files from the main database, b) transmitting changes and c) tracking changes made and their reasons. This is described in the following sections.

9.3.1 Tracking data changes

In the previous version of OrgReg, all import files have been stored in a GitLab repository, but searching for changes has been tedious. In order to change this, data deliverer got assigned the

role “data manager” in the OrgReg application and granted access to the change logs. These change logs show all changes in the data (including a comment on why a change has taken place) and can be exported into MS-Excel. This allows data managers to search for changes using the ETER ID, a specific date, country or text. This new feature improves the reproducibility of former changes significantly and will save valuable resources of the participating team members.

Additionally, the handling of deleted entities has been improved. Starting with OrgReg 2.0, deleted entities will not be deleted from the database, but flagged as “inactive”. This means that they still exist in the dataset, but are not shown for users anymore. This approach has several advantages: (1) entities will not disappear without comment and added at a later stage from other data deliverers; (2) it is not possible to re-use IDs from deleted entities, since the import mechanism does not allow import of “inactive” entities; (3) if necessary, the process of deletion can be reversed by the administrator without losing information.

9.3.2 Adding new data and revising data

This section describes the new workflow for handling the OrgReg register files. The objective of this description is to adapt the standardized process implemented in the first RISIS project in order to enable the tracking of changes in the files and restore previous versions if necessary. The improvement compared to the latest process is implementation of the role of data manager. Data managers can export data collection templates in the web application and see the export history in order to see which files have been edited lately. Additionally, data managers have access to the change logs in order to comprehend previous changes in the database.

The version control system **git** will be further used in this process. While the git-system runs in the background, the data are managed via GitLab, a git repository manager (also open-source) running on a server of JOANNEUM RESEARCH. A repository is the digital archive, where files are stored, managed and tracked by their version. Each data manager has been given a GitLab account and is member of the GitLab group “RISIS”.

Workflow

Git is usually used for source code management. Many of the functionalities of git do not work with Microsoft Office files (e.g. merging files, highlighting changes), but it enables tracking the register files by date and time of change as well as the person making these change.

The workflow will be organized the following way:

- A centralized workflow with a central repository (archive) on a server of JOANNEUM RESEARCH will be implemented. Each data manager will have a GitLab account, where files and any changes can be comprehended.
- The current repository will be kept for reproducibility of changes. We will remove all files in the repository and start from scratch, in order to use only data from the database.
- Data managers, who want to edit data, need to go the OrgReg application (register.orgreg.joanneum.at) and download the data collection templates.
- Data are edited and uploaded via git.
- The administrator imports the data in the database and makes the data checks.

The following chapter explains in a detailed way the necessary steps for implementing the system.

First steps

We will keep the current git repository, but start from scratch (the repository is empty). This means that the files in your local repository will be deleted in order to use only data from the database. This prevents usage of old data versions (although not visible in your local repository, you can always retrieve each file you ever pushed to the repository).

Please log in to your account and make the following request: `git pull origin master`.

Now every user has the same status of the repository on his or her locale system (at the beginning, it is empty).

Retrieve and/or send changes to the repository

In order to change register files or add new files to the repository, follow these steps:

1. Access the register application: <https://register.orgreg.joanneum.at/> and log in.
2. Go to menu `Collection Data Export`.
3. Choose country and export the data collection file. You can see in the export history, which files have been exported lately. If the file you want to edit was exported in the last week, please contact the administrator in order to see, if the file is still being used. **Please do not edit files before you get feedback from the administrator!**
4. Edit the data collection file and save it into the repository.

IMPORTANT NOTE: here we have two differences to the last process:

- a. When you save the file to the repository, the name of the file needs to be the same for each country every time. Usually, the name is correct when you export the file (exception: several exports, where you can get a suffix to the name). The pattern should be: "data_collection_template_[CountryCode].xlsx".
- b. If you make changes, it is obligatory to comment the reason of change. You will find in each table of the data collection files one column, which is used for commenting changes (last column of each table, "Explanation of changes in entity table", "Explanation of changes in entity table" etc.). This variable was introduced only for data managers in order to allow a better tracking of changes.

5. Again, go into the folder `register_files_repository`, click the right mouse button and select option `Git Bash Here`.
6. Type the following and confirm with `Enter` after each command:
 - a. `git pull origin master` (this is necessary in order to avoid conflicts)
 - b. `git add .`
 - c. `git commit -m "a meaningful text"`
 - d. `git push origin master`

```
wad@POLL123 MINGW64 /d/register_files_repository (master)
$ git add .

wad@POLL123 MINGW64 /d/register_files_repository (master)
$ git commit -m "added file for AT"
[master (root-commit) 40eee9b] added file for AT
1 file changed, 0 insertions(+), 0 deletions(-)
create mode 100644 register_AT_final.xlsm

wad@POLL123 MINGW64 /d/register_files_repository (master)
$ git push origin master
Counting objects: 3, done.
Delta compression using up to 4 threads.
Compressing objects: 100% (3/3), done.
Writing objects: 100% (3/3), 61.55 KiB | 7.69 MiB/s, done.
Total 3 (delta 0), reused 0 (delta 0)
To https://gitlab.wibis-steiermark.at/RISIS/register_files_repository.git
* [new branch]      master -> master
```

7. The changes and/or additions have now been “pushed” to the repository and each user can update his or her repository by pulling the changes (see point 2.a).
8. If done, exit the command prompt by typing `exit`.

Track changes in GitLab

These previous chapter has included all the necessary steps to implement a version control system for the OrgReg register files. In order to have a look at the history of the files, you can do the following:

1. Enter your GitLab account.
2. Go to `Repository` -> `Commits`
3. The single commits are time-stamped and include all the files where changes have been made and which have been sent to the repository (see screenshot below). In this way, we can track the changes and always go back to a previous version if necessary.

The screenshot shows the 'Commits' page for the 'register_files_repository' on the 'master' branch. It lists three recent commits by Daniel Wagner-Schuster:

- undo changes in AT0001** (a950882b) - 6 minutes ago
- change in AT0001** (a83ddbbae) - 10 minutes ago
- added file for AT** (40eee9b2) - about an hour ago

The GitLab account allows you to have a look at the latest status of each file. Go to **Repository** -> **Files** and check if the repositories on GitLab and on your local copy include the same files. Also, please check if the date and time of the last update are the same.

The screenshot shows the 'Files' page for the 'register_files_repository' on the 'master' branch. It displays a table of files in the repository:

Name	Last commit	Last update
register_AT_final.xlsxm	added file for AT	about a minute ago